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List of Abbreviations

AD Automated Driving

ASAM Association for Standardisation of Automation and Measuring Systems

CAMeOnto Context awareness meta ontology modeling

CG-Reman Cross-Generational Remanufacturing

COD Current Operational Domain

CV Carryover Variation

DRM Design Research Methodology

DS I Descriptive Study I

DS II Descriptive Study II

EV Embodiment Variation

HQDM High Quality Data Model

OD Operational Domain

ODD Operational Design Domain

OWL Web Ontology Language

PPE Personal Protection Equipment

PS Prescriptive Study

PV Principle Variation

RC Research Clarification

RDF Resource Description Framework

RQ Research Question

SGE System Generation Engineering

SPARQL SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language

SWRL Semantic Web Rule Language

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1 Introduction and Motivation

In recent years, sustainable development has become a dominant trend in both industry and research, reflecting the urgent need to balance economic growth with ecological responsibility (United Nations [2015](#); Purvis, Mao, and Robinson [2019](#)). Within this context, the circular economy plays a central role by promoting restorative and regenerative industrial systems that minimise waste and close material loops (Geissdoerfer et al. [2017](#)). In contrast to the traditional linear “take–make–dispose” model, the circular economy conceives the end of a product’s life as the beginning of a new cycle (Kalmykova, Sadagopan, and Rosado [2018](#)).

Among the various strategies that operationalise the principles of the circular economy, *re-manufacturing* is of particular importance. By restoring used products or components to a like-new condition, remanufacturing not only conserves material resources but also extends product lifecycles and generates economic value from reuse (Fofou, Sundin, and Sakao [2021](#)). It therefore represents a promising pathway to reconcile ecological and economic objectives, while simultaneously reducing waste and dependence on virgin resources.

However, product development is increasingly shaped by rising complexity, growing uncertainty, and the impact of global megatrends such as digitalization (Hallstedt, Isaksson, and Öhrwall Rönnbäck [2020](#)) and sustainability transitions (Vlajić et al. [2025](#)). These dynamics intensify the challenges of remanufacturing, making it difficult for companies to address technical, economic, societal, and environmental constraints simultaneously. Coping with this complexity requires systematic methods that enable a deeper understanding of system information—including evolving user requirements, reusable component characteristics, and emerging improvement needs.

One effective way to derive and structure such information is through scenarios, which provide a valuable tool for information structuring and strategic planning (Alexander Fink and Siebe [2016](#)). In the context of circular product systems, however, it is necessary to explicitly consider users and customers in order to obtain systematic depictions of procurement and application processes. This perspective enables the identification of potential edge and corner cases that derive and validate requirements for subsequent product generations. At the same time, they can integrate additional aspects, such as patterns of component use, environmental conditions, and potential improvement opportunities. In this way, scenarios not only support strategic decision-making in remanufacturing but also provide foresight for the development of future product generations—for example, in the case of the angle grinder. A clear understanding of customer and user scenarios allows more reliable decisions on component reuse and, if necessary, helps restrict permissible applications when components face limited performance (e.g., reusing parts from a “heavy-use” product in a “light-use” context).

To systematically represent such multifaceted scenarios, this thesis explores an ontology-based modeling approach, inspired by methods from the field of autonomous driving—such as the OpenXontology (ASAM e. V. [2022](#)) and scenario-based validation frameworks (De Gelder et al. [2022](#)). Although an ontology as a conceptual model is not inherently machine-readable, its formalisation within Protégé enables a logically consistent and computable representation of complex relationships between users, customers, products, components, and contexts. In this way, customer and user scenarios can be structured to support transparent analysis and reuse assessment while also providing a reusable knowledge base.

1.1 Focus and Goal

This thesis focuses on developing a structured, ontology-based approach for formalizing *customer and user scenarios* in product development within the context of power tools. Anticipating such scenarios is essential to understanding how requirements evolve across product generations, thereby supporting both the identification of improvement needs and the assessment of reuse potentials in remanufacturing. The research process is twofold. First, it analyses existing approaches to customer and user scenario modeling and evaluates the applicability of ASAM-related standards—most notably OpenXOntology, OpenODD, and OpenSCENARIO—for representing customer and user perspectives. Second, it synthesizes empirical insights from surveys, interviews, and supplementary sources into a machine-readable ontology that establishes a consistent knowledge base for future decision-making.

The resulting ontology combines a *core ontology layer*, grounded in general modeling principles, with a *domain ontology layer* tailored to customer and user scenarios in the power tool sector. Implemented in Protégé, the model enables a formalized and machine-readable representation of scenario elements and their interrelations. In this way, ontology-based scenario modeling goes beyond static documentation and establishes a structured knowledge base that supports requirement foresight, improvement identification, and reuse assessment.

The angle grinder serves as the case study within the Collaborative Research Center “Circular Factory for the Eternal Product”. Its comparatively simple structure makes it a practical and transparent research object, while its technical and application-related complexity offers sufficient depth to evaluate the feasibility of the proposed ontology under realistic industrial conditions (Thapa et al. 2025).

1.2 Structure

The thesis proceeds from theoretical foundations to empirical findings, model development, and reflection (see Fig. 1).

Chapter 2 introduces the theoretical background and state of the art. It covers concepts of system generation, the role of scenarios, ontology frameworks, ASAM-related standards, and the ontology editor Protégé. Together, these provide the conceptual basis and highlight the research gap.

Chapter 3 defines the research goal and questions and outlines the chosen methodology. Following the Design Research Methodology, it explains the sequence of activities: literature review, empirical data collection, assessment of ASAM standards, ontology construction, and the validation concept.

Chapter 4 presents the results. These include the literature review findings (addressing RQ1), the empirical scenario database, the applicability analysis of ASAM standards (RQ2), the construction of a dedicated ontology model for customer and user scenarios (RQ3), and a proposed validation approach (RQ4).

Chapter 5 provides a discussion of the results. It elaborates how the ontology supports the

identification of improvement requirements and reuse potentials, and critically reflects on the model's strengths, limitations, and areas for improvement.

Chapter 6 concludes the thesis with a summary and outlook. The research questions are systematically answered, followed by practical recommendations and directions for future work.

Figure 1: Structure of the thesis

2 State of the Art

The following chapter introduces the research fields that provide the foundation for this thesis. First, the concept of System Generation Engineering (SGE) is presented to identify the research gap, especially regarding cross-generational product development and component reuse. To address these challenges, it is essential to clarify the notion of scenarios and examine how scenario modeling represents user and customer behaviours across product generations. Ontology-based approaches are investigated as a promising means of implementing scenario modeling. Established frameworks such as High Quality Data Model (HQDM), Context awareness meta ontology modeling (CAMEnto), and the Association for Standardisation of Automation and Measuring Systems (ASAM) OpenXOntology serve as methodological references for developing a dedicated user and customer scenario model. In addition, ASAM OpenODD and ASAM OpenSCENARIO are examined, while Protégé and its plug-ins are considered practical tools within the research scope.

2.1 System Generation

A system generation refers to a socio-technical system that is recognized as a distinct entity, clearly differentiated from prior systems. This distinction is typically based on specific characteristics such as functionality, performance, cost, or aesthetic features (Albers, Rapp, Birk, et al. 2017). In many instances, identifiers such as the project name or market launch date also contribute to defining the boundaries between generations (Albers, Bursac, and Rapp 2016). In the context of industrial products, the term product generation is commonly used interchangeably with system generation. A typical example of product generations is represented by vehicles of a series, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Different product generations of a BMW

Building on this foundation, the following subsections examine three perspectives on system generations. Section 2.1.1 introduces System Generation Engineering (SGE), a structured, reference-based approach for systematically developing new product generations. Section 2.1.2 discusses Cross-Generational Remanufacturing (CG-Reman), which strategically extends product lifecycles by reintegrating components from older generations. Finally, Section 2.1.3 highlights the lack of systematic frameworks for identifying user requirements and critical functions for CG-Reman. To address this gap, we propose an ontology-based scenario modeling method, with the methodology detailed in Chapter 3.2 and the results presented in Chapter 4.

2.1.1 System Generation Engineering

SGE refers to the structured development of a new system generation based on a reference system. Any product development activity—whether for commercial release or internal validation—can be understood as part of this process. The reference system provides the foundational elements for the new generation and may consist of prior in-house products, conceptual studies, prototypes, or systems from competitors or other domains.

A structured reference-based approach to system generation was formalized by Albers, Bursac, and Rapp (2015). It rests on two central hypotheses: (1) the development of any new system generation builds upon existing reference products, and (2) the transformation from reference to new generation occurs through three distinct types of variation:

- **Carryover Variation (CV):** Direct reuse of subsystems or components from the reference product, typically requiring only minor interface adjustments.
- **Embodiment Variation (EV):** Modification of subsystems at the embodiment level, while retaining the original design principle.
- **Principle Variation (PV):** Development of subsystems based on entirely new design principles. PV inherently includes embodiment changes and represents the most innovative form of variation.

These variation types define the architecture of a new system generation. CV contributes efficiency and stability, whereas EV and PV represent the innovation share, allowing teams to strategically balance reuse and novelty.

Formally, a new product generation G_{n+1} consists of:

$$G_{n+1} = CS_{n+1} \cup ES_{n+1} \cup PS_{n+1}$$

where CS_{n+1} are carryover subsystems, ES_{n+1} are embodiment variation subsystems, and PS_{n+1} are principle variation subsystems.

The share of carryover subsystems, $\delta_{CV\ n+1}$, is given by:

$$\delta_{CV\ n+1} = \frac{|CS_{n+1}|}{|G_{n+1}|} = \frac{|CS_{n+1}|}{|CS_{n+1} \cup ES_{n+1} \cup PS_{n+1}|} \quad [\%]$$

Figure 3 illustrates the application of the SGE model to the Tesla Roadster, both with and without the explicit representation of its reference system. In this example, the reference system comprises selected elements and their interrelations, serving as the foundation for developing the new product generation. Adaptations include modifying the chassis to accommodate a shifted centre of mass and establishing new operating conditions for the battery cells due to their integration into a vehicle. The resulting product generation is achieved through a combination of carryover variation, embodiment variation, and principle variation, enabling clear functional and performance distinctions from the reference product.

Figure 3: Model without and with the "reference system" using the Tesla Roadster as an example. Source: Albers, Rapp, Spadinger, et al. (2019)

2.1.2 Cross-Generational Remanufacturing

The concept of cross-generational thinking—considering multiple product or system generations in a planned and coordinated manner—is a central principle of the SGE model (Albers and Rapp 2022). Within this framework, product evolution is not viewed as isolated, single-generation development, but rather as a continuous and strategically guided process spanning several generations. One concrete strategic application of this principle is Cross-Generational Remanufacturing (CG-Reman), which specifically targets the extension of product lifecycles by selectively re-integrating components from older generations into the most recent generation of products. To clarify the scope of this concept, Tusch, Jäckle, and Albers (2024) define CG-R as follows:

Cross-Generational Remanufacturing is a planned and anticipated industrial process of restoring a used product/system from an older generation to a product/system of the latest generation with original as-new condition and performance. From the customer and user perspective, the generated products/systems are offered on the primary market with additional inherent sustainability.

This definition explicitly extends beyond traditional remanufacturing by (1) requiring the deliberate transition to the latest product generation, and (2) positioning the remanufactured product as a primary-market offering with performance and perceived value equivalent to newly manufactured products. Such requirements place higher demands on design compatibility, quality assurance, and strategic alignment across generations.

From a quantitative perspective, Hapuwatte, Badurdeen, and Jawahir (2023) developed a mathematical model to determine when intergenerational component commonality yields the greatest benefit. Their analysis shows that benefits peak when the ratio between the average time in use (i.e., average useful life) and the time in market of a given product generation lies between 0.25 and 2. This range indicates that products whose market cycle length is broadly comparable to their usage life cycle are particularly well-suited for CG-Reman, as components from older generations can be reintegrated without excessive degradation or obsolescence. Power tools often fall within this range due to their robust construction, moderate innovation cycles, and relatively stable market demand—making them strong candidates for cross-generational remanufacturing strategies, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Proposal for circular design strategies to be investigated with priority based on product and market characteristics. Source: Hapuwatte, Badurdeen, and Jawahir (2023)

2.1.3 Interim Conclusion

Section 2.1.2 highlighted both the conceptual clarity of CG-Reman and the potential of power tools for its application. Nevertheless, Tusch, Jäckle, and Albers (2024) emphasizes that no standardized, domain-specific methodology currently exists for systematically implementing CG-Reman. In particular, practical frameworks for identifying valuable and requirement-compliant functions across generations remain underdeveloped. To determine which components are relevant for CG-Reman in the context of power tools, it is first necessary to capture the underlying system information—such as usage conditions, component characteristics, and contextual factors—and then to derive user requirements together with the functions most critical to fulfilling them. This challenge highlights the potential role of scenarios, which may serve as a means of eliciting such information and representing the functions most important across generations (see Section 2.2).

2.2 Scenarios

Scenarios are widely used in fields such as strategic planning, product development, and systems engineering, where they play a crucial role in anticipating alternative developments and supporting decision-making under uncertainty. To examine whether scenario techniques can also support CG-Reman, this section introduces their fundamental concepts and methods.

Section 2.2.1 defines the concept and types of scenarios. Section 2.2.2 addresses the user and customer perspectives and then establishes their definition for use throughout the thesis. Finally, Section 2.2.3 presents established methods for scenario construction.

2.2.1 Fundamentals of Scenarios

This subsection introduces the fundamental aspects of scenarios as a basis for their application in engineering and product development. Section 2.2.1.1 provides general definitions of scenarios, followed by a distinction between different scenario types in Section 2.2.1.2. Finally, Section 2.2.1.3 summarizes the key insights and emphasizes that scenarios can support the exploration of user requirements and the improvement possibilities of reusable components in the context of CG-Reman.

2.2.1.1 Definitions of Scenarios

The term scenario originates from the Greek word *skene*, referring to the stage or setting of a play. It was later adopted into Italian (*scenario*) and Latin (*scaenarium*) to denote a sequence of scenes or a dramatic outline (Siebe 2018). Today, the concept of a scenario is employed across multiple disciplines and has been defined in various ways. Broadly, two complementary perspectives can be distinguished: scenarios as future-oriented descriptions and scenarios as present-oriented simulations.

From a future-oriented perspective, scenarios are commonly understood as structured, consistent, and plausible descriptions of possible future situations. Durance and Godet (2010) defines scenarios as instruments for integrating potential future realities into present-day decisions, emphasizing that scenarios are not predictions but means of preparing for possible and desirable futures. Similarly, Gausemeier et al. (1998) describe scenarios as comprehensible descriptions of possible future situations derived from networks of influencing factors. Alexander Fink and Siebe (2016) contribute a foresight-oriented perspective in which scenarios represent long-term, strategic images of potential future states, rather than narrow predictions. These definitions highlight the role of scenarios in foresight, strategic planning, and long-term product development.

From a present-oriented perspective, scenarios are used as simulations of current or near-term conditions to analyze, test, or communicate system behavior. In human–computer interaction and requirements engineering, Carroll (1993) defines scenarios as narrative descriptions of what users do and experience when interacting with a system, thereby capturing real tasks in a concrete context. In simulation and training domains, scenarios represent specific sequences of conditions, events, and actions that model real-world situations for evaluation or risk assessment (Simulation Interoperability Standards Organization (SISO) 2018).

Taken together, these perspectives show that scenarios can either represent alternative futures or simulated presents, depending on their disciplinary context. This duality highlights both their analytical breadth and their methodological versatility.

2.2.1.2 Types of Scenarios

Scenarios can be distinguished by their underlying purpose and methodological orientation, illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Overview of scenario type

A fundamental distinction, illustrated by Mietzner (2009), lies between explorative and anticipative scenarios. Explorative scenarios begin with the current situation as a starting point. From this baseline, they project a variety of possible developments into the future by systematically combining alternative evolutions of key factors. They are guided by “What if?” questions (e.g., What if market demand shifts unexpectedly? What if new technologies emerge?). The purpose of such scenarios is not to predict a single outcome but to structure uncertainty, reveal interdependencies, and provide a spectrum of plausible development paths. Anticipative scenarios, in contrast, start from a predefined or desired image of the future, such as a strategic vision, sustainability goal, or target state of a system. Working backwards from this target, the method identifies which steps, decisions, or developments are necessary to make that vision attainable. They are guided by the question “What must happen in order to . . . ?” (e.g., What must happen to achieve climate neutrality by 2040?). The main value of anticipative scenarios lies in deriving concrete options for present-day action that are consistent with long-term objectives.

Beyond this basic differentiation, additional scenario types serve more specific purposes. Environmental scenarios (Andreas Fink and Siebe 2016) focus exclusively on external, uncontrollable factors, making uncertainties and dependencies visible. Action scenarios (Andreas Fink and Siebe 2016), by contrast, concentrate on actively shapeable development paths and support the derivation of concrete strategies or measures, for instance in product development or corporate strategy.

Another classification is based on the level of analysis, as outlined by Kosow and Gaßner (2008). Micro-scenarios capture products, processes, and user groups with a short- to medium-term perspective. Meso-scenarios address organizations, industries, and networks, thereby supporting strategy and structural decisions within a medium time horizon. Macro-scenarios, finally, consider long-term and highly uncertain societal and global developments, such as world economic dynamics or sustainability trends. Functional interdependencies exist between these lev-

els: global developments influence industries and organizations, which in turn affect products, processes, and user behavior. Hence, micro-scenarios gain explanatory power when considered together with meso- and macro-level scenarios, forming a coherent picture of possible developments.

In addition to general scenario classifications, product engineering distinguishes between user scenarios and customer scenarios as specific types (IPEK – Institut für Produktentwicklung 2023). User scenarios capture the context of product use, while customer scenarios represent the perspective of purchasing and decision-making. Together, these types extend traditional scenario classifications by explicitly linking scenarios to both usage and acquisition contexts. A more detailed discussion is provided in Section 2.2.2.

2.2.1.3 Interim Conclusion

Section 2.2.1.1 reviewed different definitions of scenarios, showing that they can be understood either as future-oriented instruments that describe possible and desirable long-term developments, or as present-oriented simulations that model concrete usage or decision-making situations. Section 2.2.1.2 then outlined several classification schemes: explorative and anticipative scenarios differ in their temporal logic, environmental and action scenarios distinguish between external and actively shapeable factors, and micro-, meso-, and macro-scenarios capture different levels of analysis from products and users to organizations and global trends. In addition to these general classifications, user and customer scenarios further extend the perspective by linking scenario modeling directly to product usage contexts and market conditions.

Taken together, these perspectives underline that scenarios serve as versatile instruments to structure uncertainty, capture complex environments, and provide systematic representations that support both strategic foresight and operational analysis. Building on this understanding, scenarios can also be applied to address the challenge identified in Section 2.1.3, namely how to determine user requirements and the improvement potential of reusable components for CG-Reman. For this purpose, this thesis focuses on customer and user scenarios, as they explicitly capture purchasing and usage perspectives. Their specific definition and justification are provided in Section 2.2.2.

2.2.2 User and Customer Scenarios in the Context of Product Engineering

Building on the present-oriented definition of scenarios introduced in Section 2.2.1.1, scenarios can be understood as narrative descriptions of what users do and experience when interacting with a system, thereby capturing real tasks in a concrete context. To apply this conception effectively in the user and customer scenario in the context of product engineering, it is essential to clarify how users and customers are defined and how their roles can be distinguished. Section 2.2.2.1 therefore introduces the definition and boundaries of the customer perspective, while Section 2.2.2.2 presents the corresponding definition and boundaries of the user perspective. Section 2.2.2.3 then provides the working definitions of user and customer scenarios that are applied throughout the thesis.

2.2.2.1 Customer Perspective

A customer is a natural or legal person who demands products or services and thereby enters into an exchange relationship with a supplier. In industrial contexts, this role is typically assumed by buyers, planners, or managers, who decide on procurement processes, negotiate with suppliers, and thus significantly influence the economic performance of an organization (Albers, Heimicke, et al. 2018).

The characteristic features of customers are summarized in Table 1. Customers act as demanders, financiers, and contractual partners, bearing warranty rights and payment obligations. Their relationship to the product is economically and transactionally oriented, and direct product use is not necessarily required. The primary focus of customers lies in cost minimization, compliance with regulations, and ensuring service and availability (Dispan 2016; Jurs 2017).

Characteristic	Description
Role and responsibility	Demander, financier, contractual partner; rights and obligations such as warranty and payment
Relationship to product	Economically and transactionally oriented; no direct contact with product use required
Focus	Cost minimization, service and availability, regulatory compliance
Context	End customers or purchasing departments within market and procurement environments

Table 1: Characteristic features of customers

Models of decision-making and relationship structures further show that the customer role is embedded in networks of actors who influence the procurement process to varying degrees (Gubanov and Chkhartishvili 2015). Customers strongly shape the economic efficiency of procurement through purchase prices, negotiation skills, and supplier management. Price and quality are central decision criteria (Dispan 2016), while research on business buyer behavior demonstrates that buyers, through their formal authority in supplier selection and contract design, play a decisive role in efficiency and cost-effectiveness (Jurs 2017).

This highlights the close connection between the economic perspective of customers and the operational conditions of users—a differentiation that is crucial for adequately representing both perspectives in scenario modeling (Albers, Heimicke, et al. 2018).

2.2.2.2 User Perspective

A user is a person who directly operates a product and applies it within specific usage contexts. This perspective differs fundamentally from that of the customer, who primarily makes procurement decisions (Albers, Heimicke, et al. 2018). At the same time, models of influence and impact relationships demonstrate that user roles cannot be considered in isolation; rather, they are embedded within social and organizational structures in which different actors with varying degrees of influence interact (Gubanov and Chkhartishvili 2015). This underlines the importance of capturing the user perspective as a distinct dimension in scenario modeling.

The characteristic features of users are summarized in Table 2. Users are essential for operational value creation: through efficient planning, structured working methods, high-quality materials, and user-friendly products, they contribute directly to productivity and quality (Jurs 2017). Health and ergonomics represent central requirements, for instance through ergonomic handles or tools that reduce strain and prevent downtime (Dispan 2016). Likewise, working comfort and the reliability of user-friendly and fault-tolerant products directly enhance process safety and productivity (Albers, Heimicke, et al. 2018; Dispan 2016).

Characteristic	Description
Role and responsibility	Operational use, handling, and task execution
Relationship to product	Practice-oriented, functional, and action-based interaction
Focus	Usability, reliability, safety, efficiency, ergonomics, feedback for product requirements
Context	Dependent on technical, local, and organizational conditions

Table 2: Characteristic features of users

In summary, user requirements significantly influence the performance of processes and organizations, while also being closely linked to the economic perspective of customers. A clear differentiation between the two roles is therefore essential to adequately account for their different yet interrelated interests in scenario modeling.

2.2.2.3 Definition of User and Customer Scenarios in the context of product engineering

Building on the role definitions introduced above, user and customer scenarios can be distinguished as specific forms of scenarios that systematically capture the perspectives of customers and users. Although scenarios in general are well established in the literature, their concrete manifestations as customer and user scenarios have so far received little attention. A systematic investigation of these forms is still in its early stages, even though their practice-oriented character is of high relevance for product development and, in particular, for the transition towards circular economy models (Dreher 2025).

According to Dreher (2025), the two scenario types in the context of product engineering can be understood as follows:

Customer Scenario. A customer scenario describes a concrete situation in which a customer interacts with a product or service, focusing on the conditions and requirements of the procurement process. It provides a structured understanding of the interplay between the customer, the product, and its surrounding context. Customer scenarios thus support the development, adaptation, or evaluation of products and services by systematically addressing economic, transactional, and organizational requirements.

User Scenario. A user scenario represents a concrete or hypothetical use situation in which a user operates a product or service in practice. It highlights relevant influencing factors, requirements, and the usage context, thereby capturing the operational interaction between the user

and the system. User scenarios serve as a basis for user-centered development, optimization, or evaluation of products, placing emphasis on usability, ergonomics, and performance under real-world conditions.

Together, customer and user scenarios form complementary perspectives. While customer scenarios emphasize procurement, decision-making, and organizational-economic aspects, user scenarios focus on operational handling, ergonomics, and process integration. Their systematic integration in scenario modeling ensures that both economic and functional perspectives are captured, which is essential for product development in contexts such as CG-Reman. The definitions introduced here serve as a guiding reference throughout this thesis.

2.2.3 Construction and Development of Scenarios

Having clarified the definitions and boundaries of user and customer scenarios in the previous sections, the next step is to consider how such scenarios can be systematically constructed. Scenario modeling provides the methodological means to transform abstract perspectives into structured representations that capture relevant contexts, actions, and relationships. To this end, a variety of modeling approaches have been proposed in the literature, ranging from qualitative narrative techniques to formalized, quantitative methods. Therefore, it is necessary to determine an appropriate method for scenario construction. Section 2.2.3.1 outlines two main approaches to scenario construction, while Section 2.2.3.2 discusses their suitability and motivates the choice of method.

2.2.3.1 Scenario Construction Methods

There are numerous ways to construct scenarios. According to Shell Deutschland Oil GmbH (2009), a fundamental distinction can be made between inductive (bottom-up) and deductive (top-down) approaches. Inductive procedures develop scenarios from specific observations or empirical data, whereas deductive procedures derive them from theoretical models or assumptions.

Table 3 and Table 4 illustrate a commonly used classification proposed by several authors (Alexander Fink and Siebe 2016; Gausemeier, Alexander Fink, and Schlake 1998; Kosow and Gaßner 2008; Siebe 2018).

Qualitative-empirical Method	Description
Desk research	Use of external sources (e.g., market studies, databases) to identify influencing factors.
Participatory approaches	Workshops, surveys, or expert interviews (e.g., Delphi method) to assess uncertain future issues (Linstone and Turoff 2002).
Creative-narrative techniques	Application of creativity, intuition, and tacit knowledge (e.g., brainstorming) to develop plausible scenarios based on a few key factors.

Table 3: Qualitative-empirical methods for scenario construction

Qualitative–empirical methods represent inductive approaches, relying on open and interpretative data collection such as desk research, participatory formats (e.g., workshops, surveys, Delphi interviews), and creative–narrative techniques like brainstorming or storytelling, shown in Table 3. These methods are particularly useful for capturing perspectives, experiences, and uncertain future developments.

Systematic–analytical methods, by contrast, follow a deductive logic and employ structured models to ensure internal consistency and validity. Typical examples include consistency analysis to test factor combinations, simulation for the dynamic modeling of complex systems, and morphological matrices that decompose problems into key factors and combine their alternatives into plausible scenarios, shown in Table 4.

Systematic–analytical Method	Description
Consistency analysis	Examination of factor combinations for plausibility and internal consistency.
Simulation	Model-based representation of complex systems for dynamic analysis of developments.
Morphological matrix	Decomposition of a problem into factors and their possible values, combined in a morphological box to form scenarios.

Table 4: Systematic–analytical methods for scenario construction

2.2.3.2 Interim Conclusion

The qualitative–empirical methods, such as workshops and expert interviews, are particularly suitable for the construction of customer and user scenarios, as they allow direct access to usage and decision-making contexts and help identify the most relevant influencing factors. However, while these methods provide rich qualitative insights, they do not in themselves offer a structured, machine-readable format that can support systematic scenario construction across product generations.

To address this limitation, this thesis takes inspiration from ontology-based scenario modeling approaches, such as the OpenXOntology framework. The basic elements and relationships are derived from qualitative–empirical methods, while the representation is implemented in an ontology-based form. In this way, the strengths of qualitative data collection are combined with the formal expressiveness and reusability of ontology models to enable the structured construction of customer and user scenarios.

2.3 Ontology

Ontologies provide a structured, formalised way of representing knowledge in a given domain. They define concepts (classes), their attributes, and the relations between them, thereby enabling a shared and machine-readable understanding of complex systems (Gruber 1993). Unlike informal models or textual descriptions, ontologies follow a logical foundation—commonly expressed in Web Ontology Language (OWL) (W3C 2012)—which allows reasoning engines to infer implicit knowledge, check consistency, and support automated analysis.

In the context of this thesis, ontologies are particularly relevant because they enable the systematic representation of *scenarios* that involve users, customers, products, and contextual conditions. Through an ontology-based approach, scenario elements can be formalised into triples (subject–predicate–object) and structured in a way that supports both human interpretation and machine-based processing.

The following subsections provide an overview of existing ontology foundations and frameworks that are relevant to this work. First, the general principles of ontology engineering are outlined in Section 2.3.1. Second, the High-Quality Data Model is introduced as a core meta-modeling framework in Section 2.3.2. Third, in Section 2.3.3, the CAMEnto methodology is presented as an ontology-based supporting method for scenario modeling in engineering contexts. Finally, the ASAM OpenXOntology is discussed in Section 2.3.4, as a domain-specific standard originally developed for automated driving, but with transferable principles to the angle grinder scenario model developed in this thesis.

2.3.1 Basics

In this section, the basic foundations are introduced, including a description of the key components of the approach, the A/TBox framework, and the potential benefits of ontology-based modeling. These elements provide the necessary background for understanding the subsequent methodological development and its application.

2.3.1.1 Components of an Ontology

A widely cited definition describes an ontology as a “formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization” (Gruber 1995). In practice, this means that ontologies formally enumerate the entities in a discipline, their relationships, and their definitions, by means of a declarative formalism. Such a formalism specifies classes (or types), attributes (or properties), individuals (specific members of a class), and the relationships among them (Gruber 1993).

Based on this definition, the core components of an ontology can be distinguished as follows (ASAM e. V. 2022):

- **Classes:** represent sets of entities in a domain, such as activities, events, places, or physical objects.

- **Individuals:** instances of these classes, which may belong to one or multiple classes simultaneously.
- **Properties:** define relationships between classes or individuals.

The combination of these elements results in statements known as *triples*, which follow a subject–predicate–object structure, as shown in Figure 6. For instance, in the assertion,

$$\text{Vehicle} \xrightarrow{\text{hasPart}} \text{Wheel}$$

the vehicle is the subject, *hasPart* is the predicate (property), and the wheel is the object. Such triples form the backbone of ontological knowledge representation, enabling both humans and machines to interpret and reason over domain knowledge in a consistent way.

Figure 6: A directed relationship from subject to object

Besides, ontologies further employ logical constructs to constrain the use of properties. A central example is *cardinality*, which specifies the number of values a property may take (Guarino, Oberle, and Staab 2009). For instance, a bicycle can be defined as a subclass of *RoadVehicle* with the restriction *hasPart exactly 2 Wheel*.

$$\text{Bicycle} \xrightarrow{\text{hasPart}} \text{Wheel}[2]$$

Such axioms combine structural descriptions with formal constraints, thereby ensuring both expressiveness and logical rigor.

2.3.1.2 TBox and ABox

The Web Ontology Language (OWL) is grounded in Description Logics, which provide the formal foundation for representing and reasoning about ontologies (Horrocks, Patel-Schneider, and Harmelen 2003). Within this framework, the structure of an ontology is commonly divided into two complementary components: the TBox (terminological component), which specifies the conceptual schema of a domain by defining classes and properties, and the ABox (assertional component), which contains facts about individuals instantiating these concepts (ASAM e. V. 2022).

The TBox specifies the schema of the ontology, including classes, properties, and axioms. For example, as shown in Figure 7, the class *RoadVehicles* may be defined to *driveOn* a *Road*, and to have parts of type *Wheels*. The class *Bicycle* is modelled as a subclass of *RoadVehicles* with an additional cardinality restriction that it must *hasPart exactly 2 Wheels*. These schema-level statements describe the general structure of the knowledge domain.

The *ABox*, in turn, contains the concrete instances of these concepts and relations. In the example, an individual *Bicycle A* is asserted as an instance of the class *Bicycle*. It is related to a specific road instance *Lincoln road in NY* via the property *driveOn*, and it is connected through two *hasPart* relations to the individuals *Front wheel X* and *Rear wheel Y*. Thus, the *ABox* provides factual assertions about particular objects, complementing the general definitions given in the *TBox*.

Figure 7: TBox and a possible ABox(cited from OpenXontology project)

2.3.1.3 Benefits of Ontology

Ontologies provide a wide range of significant benefits for both research and practice.

First, ontologies establish explicit and common definitions of concepts within a given domain, thereby reducing semantic ambiguities such as polysemy, homonymy, and inconsistent terminology that often hinder communication (Baader et al. 2003). By formalising the vocabulary, ontologies ensure a shared understanding not only among human stakeholders—such as engineers, researchers, and practitioners—but also across heterogeneous software systems and machines.

Secondly, ontologies are inherently extensible and interoperable due to their grounding in semantic web standards such as OWL (W3C 2012). This standardisation allows knowledge bases to be continuously refined and integrated with external sources, making them adaptable to evolving domains.

Furthermore, ontologies also enable advanced computational capabilities. These include semantic reasoning, similarity analysis, and automatic inference, which allow systems to uncover implicit relationships and derive new knowledge from existing facts. Such capabilities directly support applications in knowledge-intensive domains, such as semantic search, recommendation systems, information clustering, and automated classification (Horrocks, Patel-Schneider, and Harmelen 2003). In this way, ontologies not only facilitate consistent communication but also enhance the functionality, scalability, and intelligence of modern information systems.

2.3.1.4 Interim Conclusion

Ontology was chosen in this thesis as the foundation for scenario modeling for two main reasons.

First, the components of ontology align well with the requirements of scenario representation. The influencing factors and contextual data collected through qualitative–empirical methods (see Section 2.2.3.1) can be mapped onto ontological structures such as classes, relations, axioms, and instances. In this way, actors, contexts, and relationships are formalised in a consistent and structured form that ensures both human comprehensibility and machine readability.

Second, as outlined in Section 2.3.1.3, ontologies provide significant advantages such as conceptual clarity, extensibility, and computational reasoning. These characteristics make them a particularly suitable foundation for constructing structured and reusable models of customer and user scenarios.

Together, these aspects justify the use of ontology-based modeling in this thesis and provide the foundation for the methodological framework introduced in Chapter 3.

2.3.2 HQDM

High Quality Data Models (HQDM) were first introduced by West (2010) in his book *Developing High Quality Data Models*. The approach was motivated by the need to overcome common shortcomings of traditional data models, such as semantic ambiguity, inconsistent categorisation, and limited extensibility. By providing a rigorous ontological foundation, HQDM ensures that data models represent real-world phenomena in a consistent, precise, and logically coherent manner.

At its core, HQDM introduces a metamodel that defines fundamental categories of entities and relationships, together with constraints that guide the construction of domain-specific models. This provides a structured and formally grounded methodology for developing data and ontology models in engineering and related domains.

The following subsections present the key aspects of HQDM. Section 2.3.2.1 introduces the framework and its most important classes. Section 2.3.2.2 describes Express-G, the graphical notation used in HQDM concepts. Finally, Section 2.3.2.3 provides an interim conclusion and outlines the connection to OpenXOntology.

2.3.2.1 HQDM Framework and Important Classes

In HQDM framework, everything is considered either:

- **Abstract object:** a set or tuple grouping entities or relationships, such as the ordered pair representing one vehicle being in front of another.
- **Spatio-temporal extent:** an entity that exists in time and space, such as a vehicle.

2.3.2.1.1 Abstract Objects

Abstract objects are things that do not exist in space and time. They reflect our understanding of the real things. Within HQDM, *Abstract Objects* can be grouped into two subcategories: Classes and Relationships, as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Classification of Abstract Object from *HQDM project*
<https://github.com/gchq/HQDM>

The first subcategory, *Classes*, is defined as “an `abstract_object` that has members and whose identity is determined by its membership” (West 2010). In other words, a class is not an individual entity itself but a grouping that derives its meaning from the set of instances it contains. Three classes are of particular importance in HQDM:

- **`class_of_abstract_object`:** the most general category for abstract entities. It provides the root from which all other abstract groupings are derived. For example, it encompasses higher-order constructs such as “`class_of_relationship`”.
- **`class_of_spatio_temporal_extent`:** represents categories of entities that exist in both space and time. A concrete example is “`class_of_angle_grinder`”, which groups all angle grinders, or “`class_of_grinding_event`”, which groups all grinding activities. These classes define categories, not individual instances.
- **`enumerated_class`:** A class where each member of the class is known.

In addition to these three core classes, another important subclass of `class_of_spatio_temporal_extent` is the **`physical_property`**. This class represents measurable characteristics of physical objects

and is particularly relevant in engineering applications. *Example:* The rated power (900W), weight (2.1kg), or rotational speed (11,000 rpm) of an angle grinder can each be modelled as instances of physical properties.

The second subcategory, *Relationships*, specifies logical or structural connections between entities and classes. HQDM provides several common types, including:

- **Aggregation:** part–whole structures (e.g., an angle grinder aggregates a motor, a disc, and a housing).
- **Classification:** assignment of an individual to a class (e.g., “Bosch GWS 9-125 S” is classified as a member of “class_of_angle_grinder”).
- **Specialisation:** hierarchical inheritance between classes (e.g., “class_of_cordless_angle_grinder” is a specialisation of “class_of_angle_grinder”).
- **Defined Relationship:** captures important structured associations between two or more entities. *Example:* The relationship “operator uses tool” specifies roles of *operator* and *device*.

Together, Classes and Relationships provide the structural foundation of HQDM. Classes ensure that entities are consistently grouped into meaningful categories, while Relationships formalise how these categories and their members are linked. This dual structure makes it possible to model both taxonomic organisation and interdependencies in a logically coherent manner.

2.3.2.1.2 Spatio-temporal extent

All things that exist in both space and time are defined in HQDM as *spatio-temporal extents*. HQDM distinguishes two main categories of spatio-temporal extents: **Events**, which have zero temporal extension, and **States**, which extend over a non-zero duration in both space and time. The detailed classification is illustrated in Figure 9.

Events.

Events are spatio-temporal extents with a time extension of zero but an extension in space. They describe instantaneous occurrences, such as the beginning or ending of an activity, or the moment when a physical object comes into or goes out of existence.

- **Point in Time:** A subclass of Event defined as the whole of space at an instant in time. It represents the entire universe at a specific moment. A Point in Time may also be defined relative to another, e.g., “five seconds after switching on the angle grinder.” In this sense, the instant covering the whole universe at that moment is a Point in Time. *Example:* The exact instant when the angle grinder’s motor is powered on.

States.

States are spatio-temporal extents with non-zero extension in both space and time. They represent things that persist over a duration, including physical objects (such as angle grinders) and activities (such as cutting or grinding). A State can also denote a temporal part of a thing, which maintains a stable condition over a certain period. When the condition changes, a new temporal part is created, enabling HQDM to capture the identity of things through change.

- **Individual:** Whole-life individuals that represent the complete temporal existence of a thing. *Example:* The entire lifecycle of a specific Bosch angle grinder, from production to end-of-life disposal.
- **Participant:** A physical object state that takes part in one or more activities. *Example:* A grinding disc mounted on the angle grinder while cutting steel during a specific 2-minute operation.
- **Activity State:** Represents activities consisting of their participants and causing an Event. Activities describe what changes between a start and an end event. *Example:* Cutting through a metal pipe with an angle grinder, or sanding a wooden surface.
- **Intentionally Constructed Object State:** States that exist due to an act of will or agreement, typically created by humans or robots. *Example:* The angle grinder itself, the workbench it is used on, or a safety regulation that mandates the use of protective guards.
- **Socially Constructed Object State:** States that exist due to collective social agreement or institutional convention. *Example:* Money, whose value and function as a medium of exchange derive entirely from social consensus rather than its physical properties.
- **Physical Object State:** Represents physical objects, including their temporal parts. *Example:* The grinder's motor during a continuous 10-minute operation, or a cutting disc in use until worn down.
- **Period of Time:** The temporal analogue to Point in Time. Defined as the whole of space during a specific temporal interval. *Example:* The eight-hour work shift during which an angle grinder is used intermittently.

Figure 9: Classification of Spatio-temporal extent from *HQDM project*

<https://github.com/gchq/HQDM>

2.3.2.2 Graphical Notation: ExpressG

Express-G is the graphical notation of the EXPRESS language, which was formally standardized in ISO 10303-11 as part of the STEP family of standards for product data representation and exchange, and is also the notation adopted by West in his book *Developing High Quality Data Models* to illustrate the HQDM framework (West 2010). While EXPRESS itself has both a lexical and a graphical form, Express-G provides a compact and readable way of visualising data models by means of entity boxes, attributes, and relationships (ISO10303-11). It has been widely applied in engineering and manufacturing contexts as a modeling tool, since it allows both experts and non-experts to easily interpret the structure of a data schema.

In Express-G, entities are represented as boxes, and their attributes or relationships are attached via connecting lines. Mandatory attributes are indicated by solid lines, while optional attributes are typically shown by dashed lines. Relationships between entities can be annotated with cardinalities, expressed in terms of SET, BAG, ARRAY, or LIST, with lower and upper bounds specified in brackets (e.g., $S[0: ?]$ denotes zero or more instances).

As shown in Figure 10, the relationship *hasProperty* links the entity *User* to *UserProperty*. The dashed connector indicates that the relationship is optional. "Optional" means that the relationship may either exist or not, or it is not necessary to record the relationship. $S[0: ?]$ encodes the multiplicity on the *User* side (each user may have 0..* properties), while the default inverse multiplicity allows each *UserProperty* instance (e.g., *Age*) to be referenced by zero, one, or many users.¹

Figure 10: Optional Relationship

Figure 11 illustrates a second example using Express-G notation. Here, the entity *Scenario* is connected to the entity *Location* through the relationship *hasComponent*. In contrast to the optional relation shown in Figure 10, this connection is drawn with a solid line, indicating that it is mandatory. The annotation specifies that each scenario must be associated with exactly one location. It should be noted that the diagram does not explicitly show a cardinality constraint, since "exactly one" is the default assumption in Express-G and therefore can be omitted for simplicity.

In this work, Express-G has been adopted as the graphical foundation for illustrating ontology concepts. The figures are not intended as strict Express-G specifications but as simplified representations to convey the underlying logic of the ontology model. For the sake of clarity, the original notation $[0: ?]$ has been replaced with $[0: n]$ to indicate unspecified cardinalities.

¹In Express-G, optional relations (lower bound = 0) are drawn with dashed lines; mandatory relations (lower bound ≥ 1) use solid lines.

Figure 11: Mandatory Relationship

2.3.3.3 Interim Conclusion

This subsection introduced the foundations of HQDM and its graphical representation using Express-G. HQDM provides a rigorous ontological framework by distinguishing between abstract objects and spatio-temporal extents, while Express-G offers an intuitive and standardized way to visualize these concepts. In this thesis, Express-G is also applied in later modeling examples, such as the user scenario ontology (Figure 4.4.1) and the customer scenario ontology (Figure 4.4.2).

Furthermore, HQDM serves as a core conceptual basis for the OpenXOntology framework, which represents one of the key ontology approaches examined in this research. The integration of HQDM's ontological distinctions into OpenXOntology strengthens its semantic precision and extensibility. A more detailed discussion of OpenXOntology will be provided in Section 2.3.4.

2.3.3 CAMEonto

The *Context Awareness Meta Ontology* (CAMEonto) was proposed by Aguilar, Jerez, and Rodríguez (2018) as a general framework for modeling context information in pervasive and intelligent systems. Its main purpose is to provide a structured representation of entities, their attributes, and their relations, in order to support context-awareness, reasoning, and interoperability across different domains.

CAMEonto is designed as a meta-ontology, meaning that it does not prescribe a specific application domain but instead provides a generic modeling pattern that can be specialised to concrete use cases. This pattern is based on a set of core classes and their relations, which together capture the essential dimensions of context.

Figure 12 illustrates the central structure of CAMEonto. The relationships between the main classes can be summarised as follows:

- A **User** uses a **Device** or **Service**, and may be assigned a **Role**, which further defines the type of interaction.
- A **Device** may provide a **Service**, which in turn is described by a **ServiceProfile**.
- Both **User** and **Device** are locatedIn a **Location**, which is part of an **Environment** (linked via the relation has).

- An **Activity** occursIn a **Time** interval, and can be specialised into a **DomainActivity** that reflects a concrete action.
- A **Role** may also be relatedTo a **DomainActivity**, linking the actor's role to specific activities.

Figure 12: Core classes and relations in CAMEnto (Aguilar, Jerez, and Rodríguez 2018)

CAMEnto provides a context-awareness-oriented meta-ontology that captures users, devices, activities, and environments in a structured and flexible manner. Its ability to represent contextual relations across different domains makes it particularly suitable for engineering applications, where user roles, activities, and operational environments must be modeled consistently. For this reason, CAMEnto has been selected in this work as a reference model for the construction of user scenarios. In particular, its core elements and relations serve as an inspiration for structuring the ontology of the user scenario presented in Section 4.4.1.

2.3.4 ASAM OpenXOntology

The *Association for Standardisation of Automation and Measuring Systems* (ASAM) is an international organization that develops and maintains standards for automotive development, testing, and validation processes. Its standards are widely applied across the automotive industry to ensure interoperability and consistency between tools, methods, and data models.

Among these standards, the *ASAM OpenXOntology* was introduced as part of the OpenX family to provide an ontology-based framework for representing present-oriented scenarios and operational contexts in the domain of automated driving (ASAM e. V. 2022). It provides a formal semantic structure that integrates with ontology engineering practices, thereby enabling machine-readable representations and reasoning capabilities. In practice, the ontology has been implemented in Protégé, which allows users to inspect, extend, and apply the model within a widely adopted ontology-editing environment.

This subsection is structured as follows: Section 2.3.4.1 introduces the framework of OpenX-Ontology, distinguishing between its *core Ontology* and *domain Ontology*. Section 2.3.4.2 summarises the key insights and highlights the relevance of OpenXOntology for this thesis.

2.3.4.1 Framework

The ASAM OpenXOntology framework is structured into two major parts: *Core Ontology* and *Domain Ontology*, as illustrated in Figure 13.

The **Core Ontology**, or **Core Concepts**, is derived from HQDM and provides the fundamental ontological building blocks. It comprises *AbstractObject* (including elements such as *Relationship* and *Set*) and *SpatioTemporalExtent* (subdivided into *Event* and *State*). These concepts establish a generic and reusable structure that ensures semantic precision and extensibility across different applications.

The **Domain Ontology**, or **Domain Concepts**, by contrast, is tailored to the specific requirements of automated driving. It encompasses the modeling of *EnvironmentalCondition* (e.g., weather, lighting), *RoadTopologyAndTrafficInfrastructure* (e.g., lanes, intersections), and *TrafficParticipantAndBehavior* (e.g., vehicles, pedestrians, and their interactions). Together, these domain-specific classes enable the detailed representation of traffic scenarios within simulation and testing environments.

Figure 13: Simplified framework of the OpenXontology

2.3.4.1.1 Core Ontology

The core ontology of ASAM OpenXOntology represents the top-level ontology that provides the foundation for all domain-specific concepts. It defines the most general classes and relationships—such as physical objects, states, activities, and events—that are common across application areas. Each domain concept (e.g., vehicle, traffic participant, or road topology) inherits from one or more of these core concepts.

ASAM OpenXOntology adopts the HQDM framework as the basis for its core ontology. HQDM provides a four-dimensional, ISO 15926–based structure that ensures semantic rigor and interoperability (see Section 2.3.2.1). Instead of importing HQDM in its entirety, OpenXOntology selectively reuses those HQDM elements that are essential for modeling the traffic domain, including spatio-temporal extents, abstract objects, and relationships. The simplified representation of the core ontology is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Simplified representation of the core ontology(ASAM e. V. 2022)

AbstractObject

The category *AbstractObject* in OpenXOntology aligns directly with the HQDM definition of abstract objects (see Section 2.3.2.1.1). As in HQDM, it serves as the root for sets, relationships, and higher-order constructs.

Since its theoretical foundations have already been described in detail, only one special case requires further mention here: the **defined_relationship**. In OpenXontology, the `defined_relationship` class is used only for relations that are particularly complex and contain multiple layers of information, such as `ConnectionRelation`, `SpatialRelation`, and `TemporalRelation`, shown in the Figure 15.

Figure 15: Subclasses of the defined relationship

For the purposes of this thesis, such a construct is required exclusively in Section 4, where the *PriorityRelationAssertion* within the customer scenario ontology is modeled as a defined relationship.

SpatioTemporalExtent

The category *SpatioTemporalExtent* in OpenXOntolog is shown in Figure 16. It closely corresponds to the HQDM concept of spatio-temporal extents (see Section 2.3.2.1.2). It includes both *Events* with zero temporal extension and *States* that persist over a duration in space and time. As in HQDM, states cover entities such as physical objects and activities, while events capture instantaneous changes or triggers.

Compared with HQDM, OpenXOntology extends this branch by introducing the class **SpatialLocation**. A *SpatialLocation* is defined as “a State that describes the relative continuity of a position, an area, or a space that is important in a defined context”. The description of a spatial location can take various forms—topological (e.g., adjacency), topographical (e.g., terrain type), coordinate-based (e.g., GPS), or other suitable representations. *Example*: A “construction zone area” or a “lane segment identified by GPS coordinates” can each be modelled as a *SpatialLocation*.

Furthermore, OpenXOntology preserves the notion of the **wholeLifeIndividual**, which directly corresponds to the HQDM concept of an *individual*. It is defined as “a State that is not a proper temporal PartOf any other individual of the same kind”. In other words, a *wholeLifeIndividual* represents the complete temporal existence of an entity, such as the entire lifecycle of a vehicle or tool.

Figure 16: Subclasses of Spatio Temporal Extent

2.3.4.1.2 Domain Ontology

While the *Core Ontology* of ASAM OpenXOntology are grounded in HQDM and provide a generic ontological foundation, the *Domain Concepts* are specific to the domain of Automated Driving (AD).

The purpose of this layer is to define central entities and relations of the road traffic domain and to offer a consistent and expressive vocabulary for the ASAM OpenX standards. The main categories of the domain concepts are shown in Figure 17. They are:

- **Road topology and traffic infrastructure:** captures the structural elements of road environments. *Examples*: road segments, junctions, lane markings, toll plazas, temporary road structures, and traffic signs.
- **Traffic participants and their behavior:** models different road users and their associated activities. *Examples*: vehicles, pedestrians, and activities such as starting, stopping,

overtaking, or yielding.

- **Environmental conditions:** represents ambient and situational factors that influence traffic scenarios. *Examples:* weather conditions (rain, fog), illumination levels, particulate conditions, road surface conditions, and so on.

Together, these domain concepts extend the HQDM-based core ontology towards the specific requirements of automated driving, enabling machine-readable representations of traffic environments, participants, and conditions.

Figure 17: Domain concept and its subclasses

2.3.5 Interim Conclusion

In this section, the fundamentals of ontology and relevant models were discussed in detail. Section 2.3.1 introduced the general definition, components, and advantages of ontologies, highlighting their ability to provide explicit, semantically consistent, and extensible representations of knowledge. Section 2.3.2 then presented HQDM as a rigorous top-level ontology that distinguishes between abstract objects and spatio-temporal extents and offers a formal foundation for modeling entities, relationships, and states. Section 2.3.3 examined CAMEnto as a context-awareness-oriented meta-ontology, whose structure of users, devices, activities, and environments demonstrates the flexibility of ontology-based approaches in engineering domains. Finally, Section 2.3.4 discussed ASAM OpenXOntology as a domain-specific ontology for automated driving, illustrating how a layered architecture of *core ontology* and *domain ontology* can support machine-readable scenario modeling in practice.

As outlined in the interim conclusion of Section 2.2.3.2, existing qualitative-empirical methods provide valuable insights into user and customer perspectives but lack a structured, machine-readable representation that can support systematic scenario construction across product generations.

Ontologies, by contrast, inherently provide explicit definitions, semantic consistency, and extensibility, making them suitable for capturing the complexity of customer and user scenarios.

Their implementation in tools such as Protégé further enables machine-readable representations that support reasoning and reuse. Moreover, the layered architecture of ASAM OpenX-Ontology—distinguishing between core ontology and domain ontology—illustrates a transferable design principle for present-oriented scenario modeling. By analogy, this work adopts a similar two-layered approach for constructing customer and user scenarios, in which the core layer formalizes general reusable structures based on HQDM, while the domain layer specifies application-dependent details relevant to cross-generational remanufacturing.

2.4 Other ASAM Standards in Domain Simulation

In addition to OpenXOntology, ASAM has developed a set of complementary standards that support the description and simulation of domain-specific scenarios. Among these, *ASAM OpenODD* and *ASAM OpenSCENARIO* are of particular relevance. While OpenODD provides a structured means of describing operational design domains and their contextual constraints, OpenSCENARIO focuses on representing dynamic event sequences and interactions. Together, these standards enable a more comprehensive modeling of conditions and behaviours in simulation environments. In contrast to models such as HQDM or CAMEOnto, OpenODD and OpenSCENARIO are not ontology-based but rather domain-specific description frameworks. Nevertheless, although originally developed for the automated driving domain, their underlying principles remain of interest for transfer to other application areas.

2.4.1 ASAM OpenODD

ASAM OpenODD is a machine-readable standard developed by ASAM to formally describe the Operational Design Domain (ODD) of automated driving systems (ASAM e.V. 2025). Built on top of the *OpenX Ontology*, it provides a structured and interoperable way to capture the conditions under which an automated system is intended to operate. While OpenX Ontology offers the underlying vocabulary, OpenODD emphasises the explicit description of *environmental conditions*—such as road types, weather, time of day, and infrastructure—thereby defining the operational boundaries of the system.

2.4.1.1 OpenODD Taxonomy

Several key concepts clarify its scope. The ODD specifies the environmental and contextual conditions in which the system is designed to function. The Current Operational Domain (COD) represents the actual conditions perceived by the sensors during operation, which must be a subset of the ODD. If the COD exceeds the defined ODD, fallback strategies or human takeover are triggered. More generally, the Operational Domain (OD) refers to any operating environment of a system, not limited to automated driving (ASAM e.V. 2025).

Figure 18 illustrates the main structure of OpenODD, which is divided into three main categories:

- **Scenery:** structural and static features of the environment, such as zones, drivable

areas, junctions, special structures, fixed and temporary road structures.

- **Environment:** contextual conditions, including weather, illumination, particulate matter, and connectivity.
- **Dynamic Elements:** moving entities such as traffic participants and the subject vehicle.

Figure 18: Taxonomy and example representation of ODD elements (ASAM e. V. 2025)

2.4.1.2 OpenODD Presentation (DSL / Tabular / YAML)

OpenODD supports multiple presentation formats for specifying an ODD, each capturing the same taxonomy and attributes but optimized for different contexts.

The *OpenSCENARIO DSL* represents ODDs directly in the domain-specific language of the OpenSCENARIO standard (see Section 2.4.2), enabling conditions such as weather, road types, or participant behaviors to be directly embedded in simulation scripts.

The *tabular form* expresses ODDs in a spreadsheet-like table, where rows correspond to influencing factors (e.g., road type, illumination, rainfall) and columns list the allowed values or parameter ranges, as illustrated in Figure 19. This format is particularly suited for authoring, documentation, and collaborative review, since it provides a clear overview of all ODD dimensions.

Finally, the *YAML* representation encodes the same content in a hierarchical, machine-readable structure. This allows categorical conditions and quantitative attributes to be specified in a unified way. Two examples are shown below.

CONCEPT_ID	PARENT_ID	TYPE	UNIT_TYPE	AFFILIATION_SOURCE	AFFILIATION_CONCEPT	AFFILIATION_SOURCE_NAME_EN	CONCEPT_NAME_EN	DESCRIPTION_EN
environmental_conditions		record		ISO 34503	environmental_conditions	ISO 34503	Environmental Conditions	Concepts related to environment conditions
weather	environmental_conditions	record		ISO 34503	weather	ISO 34503	Weather	Concepts related to weather
wind	weather	record		ISO 34503	wind	ISO 34503	Wind	Concepts related to weather
wind_speed	wind	float	velocity	ISO 34503	wind_speed	ISO 34503	Wind Speed	Wind speed measured by meteorological sensors
rainfall	weather	record		ISO 34503	rainfall	ISO 34503	Rainfall	Concepts related to rainfall

Figure 19: Tabular taxonomy representation of OpenODD

Categorical taxonomy example:

TAXONOMY:

rainfall_level:

- light_rain
- moderate_rain
- heavy_rain
- violent_rain

fog_level: [fog_not_detectable, fog_mist, fog_medium, fog_heavy, fog_thick]

Typed attributes example:

TAXONOMY:

environmental_conditions:

weather:

wind:

wind_speed: float velocity

rainfall:

rainfall_rate: float precipitation_rate

rainfall_type:

- dynamic
- convective
- orographic

These YAML snippets demonstrate how OpenODD unifies heterogeneous information types in a machine-interpretable way. Categorical literals (e.g., `rainfall_level`, `fog_level`) enumerate discrete ODD conditions, while typed attributes with physical units (e.g., `wind_speed` as `float velocity`, `rainfall_rate` as `float precipitation_rate`) capture precise quantitative descriptions of environmental factors. Together, these formats ensure that ODD specifications are both human-accessible and suitable for automated validation and simulation.

2.4.1.3 Interim Conclusion

Sections 2.4.1.1 and 2.4.1.2 outlined the taxonomy and presentation formats of ASAM OpenODD. The taxonomy distinguishes between scenery, environment, and dynamic elements, while the DSL, tabular, and YAML formats provide complementary ways of representing these aspects for both human-readable documentation and machine-readable processing. Among these categories, the explicit specification of *environmental conditions*—such as weather, illumination, and particulate matter—emerges as the central contribution of OpenODD, as it defines the operational boundaries of automated driving systems with particular clarity and precision.

2.4.2 ASAM OpenSCENARIO

ASAM OpenSCENARIO is a standardised format for representing dynamic scenarios, developed within the ASAM OpenX framework and built on top of the *OpenX Ontology*. It supports two complementary representations: the *OpenSCENARIO DSL*², a domain-specific language designed for concise, human-readable specification of scenarios, and an *OpenSCENARIO XML schema*³, which provides a more verbose but robust machine-readable format widely supported in simulation tools. While the DSL is often used for authoring and reviewing scenarios, the XML format is typically employed for simulation execution and tool interoperability.

Whereas *OpenODD* focuses on describing the environmental conditions and boundaries of system operation, OpenSCENARIO emphasises the modeling and testing of *activities* and interactions between actors. It was originally developed for the automated driving domain, where it enables the specification of actions, manoeuvres, and conditional triggers that define how different traffic participants behave over time. For example, a cut-in situation can be modelled by describing the relative positions and speeds of vehicles together with the activity sequence that leads one vehicle to merge into the lane of another (Figure 20). In this way, OpenSCENARIO provides a structured means to capture the temporal progression of activities within a scenario.

Figure 20: Cut-in scenario example represented in OpenSCENARIO

To support execution, OpenSCENARIO scenarios can be run in simulation environments such as *esmini*, a lightweight player for XML-based scenario files (Figure 21). This demonstrates how the standard can formally represent activity flows and visualise them in virtual settings. Furthermore, OpenSCENARIO has been adopted in large-scale research projects such as *PE-GASUS* and *SET Level*, where it was used to define dynamic traffic situations for testing

²<https://www.asam.net/standards/detail/openscenario-dsl/>

³<https://www.asam.net/standards/detail/openscenario/>

and validation purposes. These applications underline the specific focus of the standard on activity-centred scenario descriptions.

However, this modeling focus remains closely tied to the requirements of the driving domain, which raises questions about its applicability to non-traffic use cases, such as customer and user scenarios in the power tool context. These limitations and their implications will be discussed in detail in Section 4.3.3.

Environment Simulator Minimalistic (esmini)

esmini is a basic OpenSCENARIO XML player

License MPL 2.0 Continuous Integration passing

Figure 21: Execution of an OpenSCENARIO file in the esmini simulator

2.4.3 Interim Conclusion

Section 2.4.1 introduced *ASAM OpenODD*, which provides a structured, machine-readable way to specify the operational boundaries of automated systems, focusing on environmental and contextual conditions. Section 2.4.2 then discussed *ASAM OpenSCENARIO*, which enables the representation of dynamic activities and interactions between actors in simulation environments. Both standards are central components of the *ASAM OpenX* family and are widely applied in the automated driving domain for scenario modeling and testing.

Although neither *OpenODD* nor *OpenSCENARIO* is ontology-based, their structured representations of context and activities highlight concepts and mechanisms that are of potential interest for this work. In particular, the question arises whether their principles can be transferred and adapted to the modeling of customer and user scenarios in the context of cross-generational remanufacturing. This possibility motivates the methodological exploration presented in Section 3.3.1.3.

2.5 Protégé

Protégé is an open-source ontology editor and knowledge management platform developed at Stanford University (Musen 2015). It provides an extensible environment for constructing, visualising, and maintaining ontologies based on standards such as OWL and Resource Description Framework (RDF). Through its graphical user interface, Protégé enables users to define classes, properties, and relations, as well as to populate ontologies with individuals. In addition, a wide range of plugins and reasoning engines (e.g., HermiT, Pellet) can be integrated to perform automated consistency checks and to infer new knowledge from existing models.

Protégé has become the de facto standard tool in ontology engineering, with applications across biomedicine, manufacturing, and autonomous systems. In this thesis, Protégé served as the primary environment for implementing the ontology model of customer and user scenarios. Its compatibility with frameworks such as CAMEnto and OpenXOntology makes it particularly suitable for aligning domain-specific scenario models with established ontology standards.

2.5.1 Protégé Basic

The basic functionality of Protégé provides the foundation for ontology development. Through its graphical interface, ontology engineers can create and manage the essential building blocks of an ontology, shown in Figure 22.

- **Class hierarchies:** Concepts can be organised into structured taxonomies (e.g., *User*, *Activity*, *Workpiece*, *Device*). This enables the systematic decomposition of a domain and supports inheritance, where properties defined at higher levels are automatically passed to subclasses.
- **Object properties and data properties:** Semantic relations between entities can be formalised (e.g., *User performs Activity*), while data properties link classes to literal values (e.g., *Device hasWeight*). Together, they provide the backbone for describing both qualitative and quantitative aspects of a domain.
- **Domain and range restrictions:** Protégé allows constraints to be defined on how properties may be used, thereby ensuring semantic validity (e.g., *Activity* must involve at least one *Workpiece*). Such restrictions are particularly important for automated reasoning and for detecting modeling inconsistencies.
- **Annotations and metadata:** Classes and properties can be enriched with labels, comments, and references. This not only improves human readability but also supports knowledge sharing and reuse across projects, as documentation is embedded directly in the ontology.
- **Individuals (instances):** Ontologies can be populated with concrete examples (e.g., a specific task “cutting steel pipe indoors”). Instances make abstract concepts tangible and provide the test cases required for query formulation and reasoning experiments.

These basic functions enable Protégé to capture knowledge in a structured, machine-readable form. They establish the foundation on which more advanced features—such as querying, reasoning, and rule-based inference—can be applied to uncover hidden relations and support decision-making in scenario modeling.

Figure 22: Basic functions of Protégé

2.5.2 Protégé Plug-ins

To extend its core functionality, Protégé supports a variety of plug-ins that facilitate advanced modeling, analysis, and knowledge extraction. The most relevant for this thesis are described below.

2.5.2.1 Reasoner

Protégé integrates reasoning engines such as HermiT and Pellet to perform automated logical inference on ontologies. Reasoners provide essential services for ontology engineering, including:

- **Consistency checking:** Identifying contradictions in class definitions, property restrictions, or instance assignments.
- **Implicit knowledge inference:** Deriving additional facts from existing axioms; for example, if an *Activity* involves a *Device* and the *Device* requires Personal Protection Equipment (PPE), the reasoner can infer that the *Activity* also requires PPE.
- **Hierarchy classification:** Automatically placing new classes or instances in the appropriate position within the taxonomy to maintain a coherent structure.

Through these capabilities, reasoning engines ensure logical soundness, enrich explicit knowledge with inferred relations, and support advanced analysis within ontology-based applications.

2.5.2.2 DL Query

The DL Query tab in Protégé provides an interface for evaluating OWL class expressions against the active ontology. With an initialized reasoner (e.g., HermiT), it supports queries over *superclasses*, *subclasses* (direct or inferred), *equivalent classes*, and *instances*. This enables both structural inspection of the class hierarchy and retrieval of individuals that satisfy complex logical conditions.

As an illustrative class-level example based on OpenXOntology, the following expression intersects two category classes:

EnvironmentalCondition and WeatherCondition

When executed with the result option *Direct subclasses*, Protégé returns the weather-related specializations *CloudCondition*, *RainfallCondition*, *SnowfallCondition*, and *WindCondition* (see Fig. 23), thereby exposing the immediate taxonomy beneath the intersection.

Figure 23: Example of DL-Query

Besides such class-structure queries, DL Query can also be used to retrieve *instances* that meet compound constraints (e.g., combinations of environmental and infrastructure conditions). A concrete instance-level example, using our scenario model and generated individuals, is presented in Section 4.4.3.

2.5.2.3 SPARQL Query

SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL) is the query language for RDF and OWL data. In Protégé, the SPARQL Query tab enables users to retrieve, filter, and aggregate information from an ontology using triple patterns. Typical applications include:

- Exploring structural relations such as subclass–superclass hierarchies.
- Extracting sets of individuals that fulfil specific conditions across multiple classes and properties.
- Performing aggregations or joins to construct structured evidence tables that support further analysis.

Compared to DL Query, which is optimised for direct class expressions, SPARQL offers greater flexibility for combining schema-level and instance-level information, as well as for generating summaries and reports from ontology data.

2.5.2.4 Semantic Web Rule Language

The Semantic Web Rule Language (SWRL) extends OWL ontologies with Horn-like if-then rules, thereby enabling more expressive modeling than is possible with Description Logic alone. A SWRL rule consists of an *antecedent (body)* and a *consequent (head)*; whenever the conditions in the antecedent are satisfied, the consequent is inferred automatically.

For instance, a domain-specific rule may be expressed as:

```
IF (HighDust  $\wedge$  Indoor  $\wedge$  Cutting) THEN ImprovedDustExtraction.
```

In this example, whenever an instance combines high dust levels, an indoor environment, and a cutting activity, the ontology infers an associated requirement for enhanced dust extraction.

By formalising such recurring constellations, SWRL allows implicit domain knowledge (e.g., safety precautions, ergonomic needs, or maintenance requirements) to be made explicit and reusable. This strengthens the link between abstract ontology models and actionable engineering insights. Another example of SWRL is provided in Section 5.1.2.

2.5.3 Interim Conclusion

The preceding sections outlined Protégé's core capabilities and its extensibility. At the basic level, Protégé supports the construction of class hierarchies, object/data properties, domain-range constraints, annotations, and individuals, thereby providing a structured, machine-readable representation of domain knowledge. Its plug-in ecosystem extends these foundations with DL Query and SPARQL for expressive retrieval, description-logic reasoners (e.g., HermiT, Pellet) for consistency checking and classification, and rule support (e.g., SWRL) for capturing domain-specific if-then knowledge.

Against this backdrop, Protégé is adopted in this work for three reasons: (i) it is widely used and regarded as a de facto standard in ontology engineering, and OpenXOntology artifacts are commonly authored and maintained in formats that Protégé handles natively, which facilitates direct reuse; (ii) its mature plug-in ecosystem enables advanced analysis—combining querying, automated reasoning, and rule-based inference within a single environment; and (iii) its strict adherence to open standards (OWL/RDF) and support for interoperable, text-based serializations (e.g., TTL, RDF/XML) promote reproducibility, version control, and integration with external toolchains (e.g., simulation and analytics). Together, these factors make Protégé a suitable and sustainable platform for developing and evaluating the ontology-based scenario models used in this thesis.

3 Research goal and Approach

This chapter defines the research framework of the thesis. It begins by identifying the research gaps and deriving the main research questions (see Chapter 3.1). Based on these, the chapter outlines the research approach and describes the methods selected to answer the questions (see Chapter 3.2).

3.1 Goal of the Thesis

The objective of this thesis is derived from the identified research gaps and the resulting questions. This chapter outlines the overall research aim by first establishing the need for a structured modeling of user and customer scenarios in the context of cross-generational product development. Based on this need, the central research questions are defined.

3.1.1 Research gaps

The review presented in Chapter 2 examined relevant fields, including System Generation Engineering, Cross-Generational Remanufacturing, scenario, ontology, ASAM Standards, and Protégé.

As outlined in Section 2.1, SGE and CG-Reman provide essential foundations for cross-generational product development. SGE offers a structured framework for balancing reuse and innovation, while CG-Reman extends product lifecycles by reintegrating components from earlier generations. However, a key limitation remains: there is no standardized, domain-specific methodology that systematically captures the relevant system information—such as usage conditions, component characteristics, and contextual factors—and then derives user requirements and the critical functions that determine component suitability for reuse across generations.

Building on this, Section 2.2 examined scenarios as a potential means to address this gap. Customer and user scenarios were introduced as present-oriented instruments, capturing what actors do and experience in procurement and usage contexts. Customer scenarios describe decision-making situations shaped by economic and organizational considerations, while user scenarios focus on operational interactions and requirements such as ergonomics, safety, and efficiency. Together, these perspectives can provide insights into requirements and reusable functions. However, although qualitative–empirical methods such as workshops and interviews are well-suited to constructing such scenarios, they lack a structured, machine-readable representation that would enable systematic implementation across product generations.

In response to this shortcoming, Section 2.3 presented ontology-based modeling as a possible systematic approach to modeling customer and user scenarios. Ontologies provide explicit, semantically consistent, and machine-readable representations of concepts, actors, and their interrelations, thereby overcoming the limitations of purely qualitative–empirical methods. Frameworks such as HQDM, CAMEnto, and ASAM OpenXOntology demonstrate how domain knowledge can be formalized into reusable structures that support reasoning and

cross-domain interoperability. Although these frameworks were originally developed for other domains—most prominently automated driving—they share important commonalities with the present research context, as both rely on present-oriented scenario modeling of actors, environments, and activities. Moreover, the layered architecture of OpenXOntology—distinguishing between core ontology and domain ontology—illustrates a transferable design principle.

From these findings, the central research gap emerges: the absence of a structured machine-readable modeling method for present-oriented customer and user scenarios that supports requirement derivation in the contexts of SGE and CG-Reman. Inspired by the layered structure of OpenXOntology, this thesis develops an ontology-based scenario model and applies it to the case of the angle grinder product family.

3.1.2 Research Goal and Research Questions

Building on the identified research gap in Section 3.1.1, the overall goal of this thesis is:

To develop a machine-readable scenario model that integrates customer and user perspectives, enabling systematic understanding of the system, which can support the identification of improvement requirements and reusable components, in the context of power tools

To achieve this goal, the following Research Question (RQ) are defined:

- RQ1:** Are there existing scenario modeling methods—particularly ontology-based approaches—that explicitly address customer and user perspectives, and to what extent can they be applied or adapted to the target context?
- RQ2:** How suitable are ASAM-related standards—such as OpenXOntology, OpenODD, and OpenSCENARIO, which have been successfully applied in the automated driving domain—for modeling customer and user scenarios?
- RQ3:** If ASAM-related standards prove to be suitable (RQ2), how can a dedicated ontology-based, machine-readable model be constructed to formally represent customer and user scenarios, using the angle grinder as a case study?
- RQ4:** How can the proposed ontology-based, machine-readable model for customer and user scenarios be validated?

3.2 General Research Procedure

The structure of this thesis follows the stages of the Design Research Methodology (DRM) proposed by Blessing and Chakrabarti (2009). DRM offers a systematic framework for design research and product development and consists of four stages:

- **Research Clarification (RC)** – the clarification of research objectives and identification of research needs;
- **Descriptive Study I (DS I)** – the investigation and analysis of the current situation in order to identify needs and influencing factors;
- **Prescriptive Study (PS)** – the development of methods, models, or guidelines as potential solutions;
- **Descriptive Study II (DS II)** – the validation and evaluation of the proposed solution in practice.

Figure 24: Alignment of research questions with the stages of the Design Research Methodology

The methodological structure of this research is depicted in Figure 24. The stage of RC corresponds to Section 3.1, where the research gap is analyzed and the research objectives are derived.

DS I aims to investigate and analyze the current situation in order to identify needs and influencing factors. In this thesis, DS I consists of three complementary activities: (i) a literature review of existing ontology-based scenario modeling methods with respect to customer and user perspectives, (ii) the construction of an empirical database of customer and user scenarios, and (iii) a comparative analysis of ASAM standards to assess their applicability for scenario modeling in the target context.

PS is concerned with the development of a solution concept. Based on the insights gained in DS I, this stage focuses on the creation of a dedicated ontology-based, machine-readable model for customer and user scenarios. The model integrates empirical scenario data with ontological structures, such as HQDM and OpenXOntology, and is applied to the case of the angle grinder product family to demonstrate feasibility and relevance.

DS II addresses the validation and evaluation of the proposed solution. In this thesis, a proposal for validation is presented rather than a full empirical implementation. The validation concept outlines how the ontology-based scenario model could be evaluated. This stage thus provides a roadmap for assessing the effectiveness and transferability of the model in future research and industrial applications.

3.3 Research Methods

This section introduces the research methods applied in each stage of the DRM as adopted in this thesis. Following the overall structure outlined in Section 3.2, the methods are described in alignment with the DRM stages. In DS I, the methods for literature review, empirical data collection, and comparison with existing ASAM standards are introduced. The PS section explains the approach taken to develop the ontology-based scenario model for customer and user perspectives. Finally, Descriptive DS II outlines the proposed validation concept, describing how the developed model could be evaluated in practice. Together, these methodological elements provide the structured foundation for addressing the research questions of this thesis.

3.3.1 Descriptive Study I: Basis for Model Development

Descriptive Study I (DS I) in this thesis is structured into three activities, each contributing to a different research question or preparatory step for the Prescriptive Study.

The first activity is a structured literature review, which was conducted to answer RQ1 by identifying existing ontology-based scenario modeling methods with respect to customer and user perspectives. The detailed procedure of the review is presented in Section 3.3.1.1.

The second activity concerns the construction of an empirical database of customer and user scenarios. This step does not address a research question directly but provides the data foundation required for developing the ontology-based scenario model in the Prescriptive Study. The method for building the database is described in Section 3.3.1.2.

The third activity is a comparative analysis of ASAM standards, carried out to answer RQ2. This activity assessed the applicability of ASAM standards to customer and user scenario mod-

eling in the target context. Since no predefined methodology exists, the analysis consisted of examining the scope, modeling focus, and intended application of OpenXOntology, OpenODD, and OpenSCENARIO. The procedure is described in Section 3.3.1.3.

3.3.1.1 Method of Literature Review

The literature review was carried out following the recommendations of Arlene Fink (2019). The adapted review process is illustrated in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Literature review process (adapted from Arlene Fink 2019)

The review was further documented using a PRISMA flow chart. The procedure can be summarized in the following steps:

1. **Formulating the research question:** Defining the scope and focus of the review (RQ1).
2. **Identifying sources:** Selecting relevant databases and repositories to ensure comprehensive coverage.
3. **Defining search strings:** Operationalizing the main concepts of the research question to guarantee transparency and reproducibility.
4. **Conducting the literature search:** Systematically collecting potentially relevant publications.
5. **Screening:** Applying a two-stage procedure:
 - 5.1. *Practical screening* — excluding works that are evidently irrelevant (e.g., non-scholarly or out-of-scope).
 - 5.2. *Methodological screening* — ensuring that the remaining studies meet the inclusion criteria with respect to methodological relevance.
6. **Doing the review:** Extracting and recording information from the included studies in a structured way.
7. **Synthesizing:** Integrating findings across the reviewed literature to identify patterns, gaps, and insights in relation to the guiding research question.

The final result is provided in Section 4.1.

3.3.1.2 Method of Empirical Data Collection

To support the development of a structured ontology-based scenario model, a comprehensive empirical dataset was required. The empirical data collection was carried out using multiple complementary methods. The final integrated empirical database is introduced in Section 4.2.

Workshops for Scenario Data Collection

The organisation of the workshops in this thesis followed the widely adopted focus group methodology outlined by Krueger and Casey (2014), which structures workshops into four phases: planning, recruiting, moderating, and analyzing. Two workshops were conducted: an initial expert workshop to refine the methodology and a subsequent formal workshop to generate the empirical scenario database. The comparison is summarised in Table 5. The final template of the workshop is provided in Appendix 6.3.

Step	Initial Expert Workshop	Formal Workshop
Planning	A preliminary template was prepared to structure scenario documentation and guide discussion.	The refined template was adopted to capture both customer and user perspectives across diverse contexts.
Recruiting	Six experienced researchers from IPEK, selected for methodological expertise and familiarity with angle grinder use cases.	Broader group including experts (craftsmen, industry practitioners) and non-experts (DIY and home users).
Moderating	Facilitated format with a moderator guiding individual reflection, group discussion, and documentation using the template.	Same structured moderation process, ensuring balanced contributions and consistent documentation across heterogeneous participants.
Analyzing	Insights consolidated to refine and optimise the template for formal data collection.	Results harmonised, terminology standardised, and missing relations added; outputs transferred into the empirical scenario database.

Table 5: Comparison of initial expert and formal workshops (adapted from Krueger and Casey (2014))

Expert Interview

The expert interviews were conducted by Julian Dreher and followed a theory-based guide developed specifically for this thesis. The design of the guide was informed by recommendations for qualitative research in the management and engineering sciences (Myers 2013). Its structure aimed at systematically capturing four theoretical dimensions of scenarios: (i) structural–contextual, (ii) analytical–methodical, (iii) narrative–descriptive, and (iv) functional–transfer related (Dreher 2025). Each question was formulated to address one or more of these dimensions, with open-ended response options to allow differentiated and in-depth data collection. This ensured that all relevant aspects of customer and user scenarios could be empirically assessed and compared with theoretical assumptions. Table 6 illustrates how each

scenario dimension was operationalised through exemplary questions in the interview guide.

Scenario Dimension	Example Question from Interview Guide
Structural–contextual	Which persons are typically involved in the use or procurement of an angle grinder?
Analytical–methodical	Does a typical process for use or procurement exist?
Narrative–descriptive	Please describe a typical situation in which an angle grinder is used or procured.
Functional–transfer related	What requirements do you place on an angle grinder?

Table 6: Scenario dimensions and exemplary questions from the interview guide

The interviewees were selected exclusively among professionals with direct experience in the use or procurement of angle grinders. To ensure a broad coverage of perspectives, participants were drawn from three occupational groups: craft and industry, rescue services, and research and development.

Most interviews were conducted at the workplace of the participants, with some held in digital format. The interview guide was provided in advance, together with the invitation, allowing participants to prepare and familiarize themselves with the questions beforehand. The complete guide is documented in the Appendix and forms the methodological basis of the conducted interviews.

Online Survey.

To complement the expert interviews, an online survey was conducted among non-expert users of angle grinders. The survey targeted individuals who typically use the tool in private contexts such as home improvement or renovation projects, thus contributing to everyday usage situations in the data collection. This extended the range of possible scenarios and added perspectives that were not present in the expert interviews. The content of the survey was aligned with the structure of the interview guide, ensuring consistency across both data collection formats.

Supplementary Data Sources

To complement the primary data collection activities, additional scenario information was gathered from publicly available online sources. Blogs, industry articles, and user forums were reviewed to extract real-world descriptions of angle grinder usage and purchasing situations, with particular focus on details relevant to the identified scenario elements and operating domains. Detailed sources are provided in Appendix [6.4](#).

In cases where the number or diversity of collected examples was insufficient to represent the variety of potential customer and user scenarios fully, additional synthetic examples were generated using ChatGPT. These generated cases followed the same structural format and element definitions as the workshop template, ensuring consistency with the primary data.

The inclusion of these supplementary sources expanded the scenario variations and operational contexts, thereby enhancing the robustness of the dataset used for refining the scenario model.

3.3.1.3 Analysis of ASAM Tools for Customer and User Scenario Modeling

A structured two-step approach was applied to assess the applicability of ASAM tools for modeling customer and user scenarios:

1. **Examination of ASAM Tools and Their Scope.**

In the first step, the ASAM-related standards discussed in the state-of-the-art review—*OpenXOntology* (Section 2.3.4), *OpenODD* (Section 2.4.1), and *OpenSCENARIO* (Section 2.4.2)—were examined in greater detail. Since *OpenXOntology* is grounded in the *HQDM* (Section 2.3.2), *HQDM* was also included to capture the meta-modeling principles underlying the ontology. The purpose of this step was to clarify the conceptual scope, modeling focus, and intended application context of each tool.

2. **Comparison with the Angle Grinder Scenario Domain.**

In the second step, the identified scopes and modeling principles of the ASAM tools were systematically contrasted with the *customer and user scenario domain* of angle grinders, as characterised in the empirical database (see Section 4.2) or other online resources (see Appendix 6.4). This comparison aimed to reveal potential overlaps, mismatches, and adaptation needs, thereby determining which ASAM modeling concepts could be transferred to the power tool domain and which required redefinition or extension.

3.3.2 Prescriptive Study: Ontology-based Model Development

To address RQ3 ("If ASAM-related standards prove to be suitable (RQ2), how can a dedicated ontology-based, machine-readable model be constructed to formally represent customer and user scenarios, using the angle grinder as a case study?"), the ontology development followed a two-step sequence. This order reflects the framework of *OpenXOntology* and its foundation in the *HQDM*, both of which distinguish between *core ontology* (Section 2.3.4.1.1) and *domain ontology* (Section 2.3.4.1.2). The *HQDM*-based core ontology provides generic, temporally-aware primitives (e.g., *Object*, *Role*, *Event*, *State*), while the domain ontology specializes these primitives for a specific application area.

Accordingly, the development process first focused on constructing a *domain ontology* for angle grinder customer and user scenarios, and then aligning this domain layer with the *HQDM*-based core ontology. This procedure ensured that the ontology captured domain-specific requirements while remaining semantically compatible with ASAM-related standards. The ontology modeling and alignment were implemented in the *Protégé* environment (Section 2.5), which provided the infrastructure for class hierarchy design, relation modeling, and semantic validation.

3.3.2.1 Domain Ontology Construction

The development of the domain ontology followed the seven steps proposed in *Ontology Development 101: A Guide to Creating Your First Ontology* (Noy and McGuinness 2001). Each step was adapted to the specific context of modeling customer and user scenarios for angle grinders, and linked to the empirical database and methodological inputs outlined in Section 4.2:

1. **Determine domain and scope.**

The domain and scope were defined based on the research need (Section 3.1), focusing on customer and user scenarios of angle grinders in the context of cross-generational remanufacturing. The consolidated database provided in Section 4.2 served as the main source for identifying boundaries and requirements.

2. **Consider reusing existing ontologies.**

Elements from ASAM OpenXOntology that were identified as transferable (Section 4.3), together with modeling principles from the CAMEnto methodology, were used to structure the ontology.

3. **Enumerate important terms.**

Key terms (e.g., user roles, customer segments, tasks, environments, tool features) were extracted and summarised from the empirical database.

4. **Define classes and hierarchy.**

The identified terms were organised into classes and hierarchies using Protégé, with structure derived from OpenXontology and patterns in the empirical database.

5. **Define class properties and relations.**

Relations such as *User is participant of Activity*, *Activity involves Tool*, and *Location has Environment* were specified using data extracted from the empirical database. In addition, some selected property patterns were adopted from *OpenXOntology* and from *CAMEnto*, ensuring that the ontology remained compatible with established frameworks while capturing the specific requirements of the angle grinder domain.

6. **Define facets of properties.**

Attributes such as ranges, constraints, and contextual values (e.g., dust levels, usage frequency, power supply type) were derived from empirical data in the database. These facets were subsequently adjusted and formalised in accordance with the requirements of the HQDM and OpenXontology, ensuring that the domain-specific properties remained consistent with the underlying core modeling principles.

7. **Create instances.**

Instances of scenarios were created based on interview data, providing concrete examples of customer and user situations. These instances were implemented in Protégé to validate the ontology structure and ensure consistency (Section 4.4.3).

Through this step-wise process, the domain ontology was constructed based on empirical data, existing ontological frameworks, thereby establishing a robust foundation for subsequent alignment with HQDM core ontology.

3.3.2.2 Alignment with Core Ontology

The alignment step focused on mapping the domain-level concepts to their corresponding elements within the HQDM-based core ontology. The procedure consisted of systematically reviewing each domain class and identifying the equivalent or most appropriate core concept, thereby ensuring semantic consistency between the two layers.

For example, the *Scenario* and *AngleGrinder* classes defined in the domain ontology were aligned with the core concept *SystemState*, representing the system under consideration at a specific point in time. Similarly, the *Activity* class in the domain ontology was mapped to the core concept *ActivityState*, capturing temporally bounded actions performed by users.

This one-to-one mapping process was extended across all domain classes, covering entities such as users, environments, and tools. Where no direct correspondence was available, new domain classes were anchored to the closest core-level primitive (e.g., *Property*, *Event*, or *Object*) to preserve ontological consistency. Through this systematic alignment, the domain ontology retained its specificity for angle grinder scenarios while remaining fully compatible with the HQDM meta-modeling framework that underpins OpenXOntology.

3.3.3 Descriptive Study II: Proposed Validation Method

The purpose of DS II within the Design Research Methodology is to validate the solution that was developed in the prescriptive study. Whereas the earlier stages focused on identifying research gaps, analysing existing methods, and constructing the ontology-based scenario model, DS II is concerned with evaluating whether this model achieves its intended purpose. In particular, the validation step seeks to determine to what extent the proposed ontology enables a systematic and comprehensive representation of customer and user scenarios, and whether it contributes to the identification of relevant requirements and reusable components. Thus, DS II provides empirical evidence regarding the applicability, strengths, and limitations of the modeling approach in practice.

3.3.3.1 Reference Validation Approach: Enhance Modeling

The study of Graubeger (2022) provides a comprehensive methodological reference for the validation strategy in this thesis. Enhance modeling was developed as a structured training concept to make implicit reasoning about form–function relationships explicit, thereby enabling even inexperienced designers to apply qualitative models. At the same time, the approach was deliberately designed to allow an empirical assessment of its effect on system understanding.

The validation followed a hypothesis-driven, experimentally controlled procedure. As shown in Figure 26, the process begins with the formulation of explicit hypotheses, predicting that participants trained in Enhance modeling would demonstrate superior system understanding compared to their untrained performance. These hypotheses informed the experimental design, which was divided into four consecutive phases:

1. **Introduction.** Participants were jointly introduced to the study procedure and divided into two subgroups (A and B), each assigned a different technical system.
2. **Control phase.** Both groups first solved tasks intuitively, without methodological support, relying solely on prior knowledge and experience. This established a baseline for comparison.
3. **Training phase.** Participants then received structured instruction in EnhanCE modeling, including worked examples, and practice exercises for externalizing form–function reasoning.
4. **Test phase.** After training, the subgroups exchanged technical systems and repeated the evaluation tasks. This time, they were required to explicitly apply the EnhanCE modeling method. The exchange of systems minimized bias due to familiarity with a single artefact.

Figure 26: Validation methodology extracted from Grauberger (2022)

Finally, system understanding was measured through defined indicators such as the correct recognition of system behaviours, the identification of functionally relevant states, and the localisation of critical regions. Comparing participants' performance in the control and test phases allowed the effect of the training intervention to be isolated.

This structured procedure—linking hypothesis formulation, controlled experimental design, before-and-after task execution, and systematic measurement—demonstrates a rigorous framework for method validation. In this thesis, the same overall logic is adopted: the proposed validation of ontology-based scenario modeling is likewise structured around these four elements, ensuring comparability with established approaches. The adapted validation framework is presented in Section 4.5.

4 Results

This chapter presents the results of the study, structured in accordance with the research questions and the activities of the Design Research Methodology (see Section 3.2). Each subsection corresponds to a distinct step of the investigation, moving from exploration of the state of the art to the development and validation of the proposed modeling approach.

Section 4.1 reports the findings of the literature review conducted to answer **RQ1**, namely whether existing scenario modeling methods—particularly ontology-based approaches—explicitly address customer and user perspectives, and to what extent they can be applied or adapted to the target context.

Section 4.2 presents the empirical evaluation and analysis of the scenario database, which was compiled from interviews and questionnaires. The database provides the foundation for identifying recurring elements and relationships in customer and user scenarios, thereby supporting the ontology construction process.

Section 4.3 examines the applicability of existing ASAM standards to the power tool domain in order to address **RQ2**. By comparing OpenXOntology, OpenODD, and OpenSCENARIO with the empirical database, the analysis evaluates which concepts can be transferred, where adaptation is required, and which standards prove unsuitable.

Section 4.4 addresses **RQ3** by presenting the proposed ontology-based, machine-readable model for representing customer and user scenarios. The ontology is structured into a core and a domain layer, following the principles of HQDM and implemented in Protégé.

Finally, Section 4.5 outlines the proposed validation process for the developed model. Drawing on methodological inspiration from Enhance modeling, it introduces hypotheses, an experimental design, and measurable indicators to assess the effectiveness of the ontology-based approach.

4.1 Ontology-based Approaches to Customer and User Scenarios

As the first activity of DS I, this subsection presents the results of the structured literature review conducted according to the methodology in Section 3.3.1.1. The review was designed to address Research Question 1: *“Are there existing scenario modeling methods—particularly ontology-based approaches—that explicitly address customer and user perspectives, and to what extent can they be applied or adapted to the target context?”*. The following sections summarise the findings of the review and draw interim conclusions for their relevance to the subsequent steps of this research.

4.1.1 Literature Review Findings

The review began by defining the scope of inquiry: identifying existing scenario modeling methods—particularly ontology-based approaches—that explicitly address both customer and user perspectives in an engineering and manufacturing context. The databases selected for this review were Scopus, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, and Web of Science. These sources were chosen for their broad coverage of engineering, manufacturing, product development, and systems modeling research, ensuring that both methodological and application-oriented contributions could be captured.

To ensure comprehensive coverage of relevant literature, the search strings were designed around three conceptual components:

- **Scenario modeling:** Terminology referring to various forms of scenario-based methods.
- **Customer & User Perspectives:** Terms reflecting both market-facing and operational-use perspectives.
- **Ontology:** Terms targeting ontology-based approaches, models, and concepts.

The final search queries were constructed by combining these three components with the Boolean operator AND, and, where possible, restricting the search to the title, abstract, and keyword fields within engineering, manufacturing, and product development literature. Table 7 summarises the search string components.

Topic	Search String Component
Scenario modeling	"scenario modeling" OR "scenario modeling" OR "scenario creation" OR "scenario generation" OR "scenario technique"
Customer & User Perspectives	customer OR user
Ontology	ontology OR "ontology-based" OR "ontology model"

Table 7: Search string components used in the literature review

The screening process followed two stages. In the first stage, titles and abstracts were reviewed to exclude studies unrelated to scenario creation in engineering or manufacturing. In the second stage, full texts were examined against three inclusion criteria:

1. The work applied a formalised scenario modeling or creation method.
2. The method explicitly or implicitly addressed either customer or user dimensions.
3. The approach incorporated ontology-based concepts *or* was adaptable to ontology-based representation in a product lifecycle, reuse, or generational evolution context.

The literature review process was documented by means of a Prisma flow chart, shown in Fig 27. The literature review yielded a total of 19 records across the selected databases.

After removing four duplicates, 15 publications were screened for relevance. All 15 reports were retrieved and assessed in full. During the eligibility check, 14 publications were excluded because they did not explicitly address customer or user perspectives in scenario modeling. One additional publication was excluded for lacking ontology-based concepts. Consequently, no study fully met the inclusion criteria.

Figure 27: Prisma flow chart depicting the process of literature review

The fifteen papers can be grouped into four main themes, shown in Table 8:

1. Automated Driving and Intelligent Transportation (6 papers): focusing on safety, validation, and scenario-based methods (*1st International Symposium on Intelligent Technology for Future Transportation, ITFT 2024* [2025]; Salem et al. [2024]; Cui et al. [2025]; Barthelmess and Blais [2024]; Charmet et al. [2023]; Ma et al. [2022]).
2. Semantic Technologies and Ontology-driven Applications (6 papers): context management (Silva et al. [2022]), situation awareness (Smart, Russell, and Shadbolt [2007]), KeyGraph (Horie et al. [2004]), stakeholder communication (Shekhovtsov, Mayr, and Kucko [2015]), e-learning (Dzemydienė and Tankelevičienė [2009]), robotics (Rajapaksha and Jayawardena [2020]).
3. Safety and Protection Scenario Modeling (2 papers): critical infrastructure (Trucco and Petrenj [2014]), nuclear materials detection (Ward et al. [2011]).
4. Internet of Things Industry Applications (1 paper): supply chain (ice-snow tourism) (Wang, Fang, and Wu [2024]).

Theme	Count
Automated Driving and Intelligent Transportation	6
Semantic Technologies and Ontology-driven Applications	6
Safety and Protection Scenario Modeling	2
IoT Industry Applications	1

Table 8: Summary of Literature Topics by Theme

4.1.2 Interim Conclusion

The review shows that ontology-based scenario modeling has been applied across diverse domains, with a particular concentration in automated driving and intelligent transportation, where safety validation and testing demand large-scale scenario generation. Additional contributions were found in areas such as semantic technologies, robotics, safety and protection modeling, and industrial applications of IoT.

However, none of the identified studies explicitly addressed customer or user perspectives as scenario dimensions in an industrial or product development context. In particular, no dedicated methods exist for representing customer and user scenarios in relation to manufactured products and their generational evolution, and, as Dreher (2025) emphasizes, even specific definitions of *customer scenarios* and *user scenarios* are largely absent from the state of the art. This highlights a clear research gap: while ontology-based approaches provide valuable principles for structuring and formalising scenarios, their potential has not yet been explored for modeling customer and user perspectives in product-centric contexts such as power tools.

To address this conceptual gap, the present work adopts the role-based definitions introduced in Section 2.2.2.3—originally proposed by Julian Dreher—which clearly distinguish between customers as procurement-oriented actors and users as operational actors, and uses them as a foundation for subsequent scenario modeling.

4.2 Empirical Evaluation and Analysis of the Database

As the second activity of DS I, this subsection presents the results of the empirical data collection introduced in Section 3.3.1.2. The purpose of this step was to provide a solid data foundation for the development of a structured ontology-based scenario model in the Prescriptive Study.

The empirical scenario database consolidates all primary data collected from questionnaires and interviews. In total, 42 documented scenario cases were obtained (see Table 9), comprising 2 responses from a short pilot questionnaire (Google Form), 30 responses from the main LimeSurvey questionnaire, and 10 semi-structured interviews conducted by Julian.

The following sections present the extraction, analysis, and processing of this data with respect to both the *user* and the *customer* perspectives, which together support the subsequent construction of the domain ontology.

Source	Quantity
Questionnaire (Google Form)	2
Questionnaire (LimeSurvey)	30
Interview (by Julian)	10
Total	42

Table 9: Sources and quantities of empirical scenario data

4.2.1 User Perspective

From the user perspective, the empirical data highlight several recurring themes regarding the operation of angle grinders in both professional and private contexts.

Cutting and grinding were consistently identified as the dominant applications, supplemented by secondary tasks such as polishing, deburring, paint removal, and weld seam treatment. The range of processed materials included metals, wood, stone, plastics, and concrete, demonstrating the versatility of the tool.

Users described typical workflows as consisting of preparation (e.g., securing the workpiece, wearing protective equipment, selecting and mounting discs), execution (e.g., ensuring visibility, posture, and control during cutting or grinding), and post-processing (e.g., cleaning the tool and workspace). Both professional and private participants emphasized the importance of safety, with protective guards, dust and noise exposure, and secure handling as key concerns.

Device preferences showed a balance between corded machines, valued for power and endurance, and battery-powered models, preferred for flexibility and mobility. Across contexts, the quality and suitability of accessories (cutting discs, flap discs, brushes, etc.) were regarded as decisive for efficient use. Ergonomic aspects such as weight, vibration damping, and handle design further shaped user requirements, especially for longer tasks.

Environmental and contextual factors were also prominent in user accounts. Limited accessibility of workpieces, poor lighting, or confined spaces were frequently mentioned as challenges. Private users additionally reported working under improvised conditions (e.g., garages, gardens, or home workshops), which heightened the importance of simple handling and adaptability.

Since strong commonalities were identified across the different user accounts, a set of recurring scenario elements was extracted to provide a structured representation of the findings. These elements include:

- **User** – the operator profile (professional or private), experience level, and handling practices.
- **Activity** – the specific tasks performed (e.g., cutting, grinding, polishing, deburring).
- **Workpiece** – the types of materials and objects processed (e.g., metal bars, stone surfaces, construction parts).
- **Angle grinder attributes** – technical features such as power supply (corded or battery), robustness, and ergonomics (weight, vibration protection, handle design).

- **Working context** – environmental and organizational conditions including workspace accessibility, lighting, safety requirements, and improvisation in private use.
- **Device and accessories** – the role of discs, brushes, and other attachments, as well as the importance of compatibility and quality.

Based on these categories, the participants' statements were systematically documented and enumerated, allowing the empirical data to be translated into structured scenario elements. This structured representation enables the subsequent mapping into domain ontology classes and relations.

In addition to the empirical inputs, these categories were further enriched using online resources such as user blogs and exploratory ChatGPT dialogues. This step allowed the inclusion of additional activities, contextual factors, and device characteristics that had not been explicitly mentioned by participants but are nevertheless relevant for capturing realistic usage scenarios.

All identified elements were systematically recorded in an Excel sheet (provided as Supplementary Material). For each element, its category and the number of occurrences across data sources were documented. This structured database not only consolidates empirical and supplementary insights but also provides a quantitative foundation for the subsequent development of the domain ontology.

4.2.2 Customer Perspective

From the customer perspective, the data show how angle grinders are procured in both professional and private contexts. The interviews and questionnaire responses highlight recurring themes such as procurement triggers, product requirements, system compatibility, and organizational decision-making. Professional customers—typically workshop managers, supervisors, or procurement officers—emphasize reliability, durability, and system compatibility as key decision factors. Private customers, in contrast, focus more on budget constraints and value-for-money, while still expecting sufficient robustness and safety. Across both groups, prior experience, personal preferences, and recommendations play an important role in shaping procurement choices.

Since commonalities across participants could be identified, these were extracted as shared elements relevant for customer scenario modeling. The main classes derived include:

- **Customer role and profile** (e.g., workshop manager, procurement officer, private buyer)
- **Product requirements** (e.g., quality, robustness, budget, safety standards, ergonomics, system compatibility)
- **Decision-making process** (e.g., small enterprise owner, medium enterprise purchasing, institutional approval, individual decision in private households)
- **Device and accessories** – the role of discs, brushes, and other attachments, as well as the importance of compatibility and quality.

Similar to the user perspective, in addition to these directly collected insights, external sources such as blogs and ChatGPT-based queries were consulted to further expand and refine the identified classes, ensuring coverage of practical decision factors not fully captured in the empirical data (e.g., influence of promotional offers, warranty conditions, or after-sales service).

All identified elements were documented in an Excel sheet (provided as Supplementary Material), recording both the elements themselves and their frequency of occurrence in the data. This structured consolidation provides the empirical basis for scenario modeling from the customer perspective.

4.2.3 Interim Conclusion

The analysis of both user and customer perspectives revealed a strong degree of commonality in the responses. Regardless of whether participants described procurement decisions or usage situations, recurring elements could be identified, such as the roles of actors, activities, product features, working contexts, and influencing conditions. These recurring patterns were systematically extracted, structured into classes (e.g., *Operator*, *Activity*, *Workpiece*, *Angle Grinder Attributes*, *Working Context*, *Customer Role*, *Procurement Triggers*), and consolidated in an Excel database together with their frequencies of occurrence.

This step concludes the empirical part of DS I. By combining interviews, questionnaires, and external sources, the resulting empirical scenario database provides a structured representation of user and customer perspectives. It thereby validates the relevance of the identified elements and offers a comprehensive empirical foundation.

In the following Prescriptive Study, this database serves as the primary reference for developing the ontology-based scenario model. Specifically, the extracted classes and relations will be used to structure the domain ontology, which is then aligned with the HQDM-based core ontology to enable a systematic and reusable representation of customer and user scenarios.

4.3 Applicability of ASAM Tools

The third activity of Descriptive Study I addresses Research Question 2 (RQ2):

How suitable are ASAM-related standards—such as OpenXOntology, OpenODD, and OpenSCENARIO, which have been successfully applied in the automated driving domain—for modeling customer and user scenarios?

To answer this question, the analysis followed a two-step procedure described in Section 3.3.1.3: first, examining the conceptual scope, modeling focus, and intended application of the ASAM standards, and second, comparing these findings with the empirical scenario database developed in Section 4.2 as well as complementary insights gathered from online resources (e.g., blogs and ChatGPT). This combined comparison makes it possible to assess which modeling concepts can be transferred to the power tool domain and where adaptation or extension is required.

4.3.1 Applicability of ASAM OpenXontology

As introduced in Section 2.3.4, ASAM OpenXontology provides a semantic framework for modeling scenarios. It is structured into a *core ontology layer*, derived from the High-Quality Data Model (HQDM), and a *domain ontology layer*, which specialises these primitives for automated driving applications.

To assess its transferability to the angle grinder context, a distinction is made between *user scenarios* (focused on tool use and operational interactions) and *customer scenarios* (focused on procurement processes and decision-making). Each of these categories is examined with respect to the potential use of domain ontology elements as well as their alignment with HQDM-based core ontology primitives.

4.3.1.1 Applicability for User Scenarios.

From the domain ontology perspective, two elements from the OpenXontology show clear analogies: *EnvironmentalCondition* can be directly mapped to worksite conditions such as dust, noise, lighting, or power supply, while *Traffic Participant and Behaviour* can be reinterpreted as the user and their activities during tool operation. By contrast, *Road Topology and Traffic Infrastructure* has no equivalent and cannot be transferred. At the same time, additional domain concepts need to be introduced in order to adequately represent the angle grinder context—such as *Angle Grinder*, *Tool Component*, *Device*, and *Workpiece*.

On the core ontology level, the domain concepts identified as analogous already have corresponding HQDM primitives: *EnvironmentalCondition* aligns with *Environment*, *User* with *Role/Participant*, and *Activity* with *ActivityState*. The newly added classes (*Angle Grinder*, *Tool Component*, *Device*, *Workpiece*) can be systematically represented based on the definition from HQDM under *WholeLifeSystemComponent* or *PhysicalObjectState*, thereby extending the ontology while remaining consistent with the OpenXontology core ontology.

In summary, since analogous mappings can be established at both the domain and core ontology levels, OpenXontology can be considered applicable as a semantic foundation for modeling customer and user scenarios in the angle grinder context.

4.3.1.2 Applicability for Customer Scenarios.

From the domain ontology perspective, several concepts from OpenXontology can be partially reused for customer scenarios. The element *Actor/Participant* can be mapped to different customer roles such as purchaser, manager, or procurement officer. Similarly, *Activity* can be reinterpreted to represent procurement-related tasks (e.g., market analysis, supplier negotiation, order placement). However, elements such as *Traffic Infrastructure* or *Road Topology* have no equivalent in the customer context and cannot be transferred. Instead, domain-specific concepts must be introduced, including *Product Requirement*, *Angle Grinder*, and *Accessory*, which are central to describing customer scenarios.

On the core ontology level, these newly introduced classes can be systematically represented using HQDM primitives. For example, *Procurement Process* aligns with *ActivityState*, *Customer Role* with *Role/Participant*, and *Contract* or *Supplier Relationship* with *SocialObject*. This ensures that even newly defined procurement-related elements remain consistent with the OpenXOntology semantic structure.

In summary, although OpenXOntology originates from the automated driving domain, its abstraction through HQDM primitives allows customer scenarios—focused on procurement and decision-making—to be modeled. Applicability can therefore be established, provided that additional customer-specific classes are introduced to extend the ontology appropriately.

4.3.2 Applicability of ASAM OpenODD

ASAM OpenODD, introduced in Section 2.4.1, is a machine-readable standard for formally describing the *Operational Design Domain (ODD)* of automated systems. Built on top of the *OpenXOntology*, it emphasises the explicit specification of *environmental and contextual conditions* (e.g., weather, time, infrastructure) and thereby defines the intended operational boundaries of a system.

From our analysis, particularly by comparing OpenODD with the working context categories extracted from the empirical database of user scenario in Section 4.2, the environmental condition logic of the angle grinder domain shows strong parallels to OpenODD, although with domain-specific adaptations. While OpenODD highlights factors such as road type or traffic infrastructure, the relevant elements for angle grinder use include workplace type, indoor/outdoor setting, power supply, dust and noise levels, lighting, temperature and humidity ranges, the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), and regulatory constraints. Because OpenODD descriptions are typically encoded in YAML/JSON, these adapted condition profiles could likewise be represented in a structured format. A possible simplified YAML sketch is shown below:

```
{
  "workspaceType": ["workshop", "constructionSite"],
  "indoorOutdoor": ["indoor"],
  "powerSupply": ["battery", "cordedAC"],
  "dustLevel": ["high"],
  "noiseLevel": ["high"],
  "lighting": ["artificial"],
  "temperatureRange": {"minC": 0, "maxC": 40},
  "humidityRange": {"minPct": 20, "maxPct": 80},
  "ppeRequired": ["goggles", "gloves", "hearingProtection"],
  "exclusions": ["explosiveAtmosphere", "rain"]
}
```

The key limitation is that OpenODD is *condition-centric*: it does not model *activities* such as temporal task flows, tool operations, or customer actions (e.g., procurement and ordering). As such, while OpenODD can capture environmental conditions for user scenarios, it cannot

represent customer perspectives or the activity dimension that is central to both procurement and operational use.

4.3.3 Applicability of ASAM OpenSCENARIO

ASAM OpenSCENARIO, introduced in Section 2.4.2, was designed to describe dynamic, activity-based scenarios in the automated driving domain. It enables the specification of manoeuvres, triggers, and temporal sequences that define how vehicles and other traffic participants interact over time. In this way, it provides a structured means to formalise and test driving situations within simulation environments.

When considering its application to customer and user scenarios of angle grinders, several fundamental limitations arise.

First, the activity logic differs substantially: automated driving scenarios are grounded in two-dimensional motion and positional changes, whereas angle grinder use involves three-dimensional manipulation of tools and workpieces. For customer scenarios, such as purchasing behaviour, the activities are even more abstract (e.g., placing an online order), making them difficult to express in the terminology of OpenSCENARIO.

Second, the simulation platforms and software associated with OpenSCENARIO (such as *esmini* and other AD-focused simulators) are tailored to traffic environments and safety testing. These tools are not designed to represent non-traffic contexts and offer little compatibility with domains such as angle grinder usage or customer decision processes.

Third, the trigger and action mechanisms in OpenSCENARIO are inherently tied to traffic-related events (e.g., lane changes, speed adjustments), and cannot directly represent contextual factors of angle grinder use, such as environmental conditions, safety constraints, or task-specific tool operations.

In conclusion, while OpenSCENARIO provides a powerful and well-structured framework for automated driving, it cannot be directly transferred to the modeling of customer and user scenarios for angle grinders. Its structure, terminology, and supporting toolchain remain tightly bound to the traffic domain, leaving little applicability for product-oriented or procurement-related contexts.

4.3.4 Interim Conclusion

The analysis of the three ASAM standards shows a clear differentiation in their applicability to customer and user scenario modeling for power tools.

First, *OpenXOntology* (Section 4.3.1) demonstrates the highest degree of transferability. Both on the domain ontology level and the HQDM-based core ontology level, suitable mappings can be established. While additional concepts specific to angle grinders—such as *Workpiece*, *Tool Component*, or *Procurement Process*—need to be introduced, these extensions remain semantically consistent with the existing OpenXOntology framework. Hence, OpenXOntology provides a viable foundation for developing a dedicated ontology-based scenario model in this

context.

Second, *OpenODD* (Section 4.3.2) shows partial applicability. Its condition-centric logic is well aligned with the *working context* extracted from the empirical database (Section 4.2), making it suitable for representing environmental factors such as workplace type, dust level, lighting, or PPE requirements in user scenarios. However, *OpenODD* lacks the ability to represent activities or procurement-related processes, and is therefore not sufficient to cover customer scenarios or user task flows on its own.

Finally, *OpenSCENARIO* (Section 4.3.3) proves unsuitable for transfer. Its event–action logic, terminology, and simulation environment are tightly bound to traffic domains, focusing on manoeuvres and interactions between vehicles. These structures cannot be meaningfully mapped to tool operation or procurement activities.

In summary, among the three standards, *OpenXOntology* provides the most solid foundation for ontology-based modeling of customer and user scenarios in the power tool domain. *OpenODD* can serve as a complementary reference for capturing environmental conditions, while *OpenSCENARIO* offers little applicability beyond its original automotive context.

4.4 Proposed Ontology Model for User and Customer Scenario

In this work, ontology is applied as a formal representation of customer and user scenarios in the angle grinder domain. Building on the triple-based structure introduced in Section 2.3, scenario knowledge is modeled through explicit relations between users, activities, tools, and environments. For instance, a scenario may link a *User* to a *Cutting Task*, or a *Cutting Task* to the required *Power Tool*. Such representations ensure that scenario knowledge is both semantically precise and machine-interpretable, enabling automated reasoning and analysis.

The proposed ontology model builds on the principles of the *ASAM OpenXOntology* and the *High-Quality Data Model (HQDM)*. It was implemented in the Protégé environment, which supports the creation, visualization, and consistency checking of ontologies. A key principle of HQDM-based ontologies is reification, which also represents a major difference compared to traditional ontology modeling. Rather than expressing most aspects through *object properties* or *value properties*, they are reified into dedicated *entities* or *classes*. This reification approach enables these aspects to exist as first-class entities, allowing them to carry additional information and participate in further relations. For example, instead of modeling “dust = high” as a simple attribute, a specific *HighDustEnvironment* entity is created and linked to the corresponding activity, thereby allowing environmental conditions to be represented in a more explicit and extensible manner. In addition, and following the structure of the *OpenXOntology*, only one generic property, *hasValue*, is retained to capture essential numerical information (e.g., spindle speed or torque), ensuring that quantitative data can still be represented when required. Overall, this entity-oriented modeling strategy enhances semantic clarity, supports automated reasoning, and ensures consistency across scenario representations.

Following the *OpenXOntology* structure, the model is divided into two complementary layers: a *domain ontology layer* and a *core ontology layer*. The domain ontology layer defines classes specific to angle grinder scenarios (e.g., *User*, *Activity*, *Workpiece*, *Tool Component*, *Environment*), while the core ontology layer provides generic primitives from HQDM (e.g.,

Object, Role, Event, State). Each domain class is systematically mapped to its corresponding HQDM-based core class, thereby ensuring semantic consistency with established ontological standards.

Within this framework, customer scenarios and user scenarios are modelled in accordance with the definitions introduced in Section 2.2.2.3. Although both originate from the empirical scenario database, their emphases diverge:

- **Customer scenarios** describe situations in which a customer engages with a product or service, focusing on the conditions of procurement, such as purchasing drivers, social environment, and contractual or regulatory constraints (Dreher 2025).
- **User scenarios** represent concrete or hypothetical usage situations, capturing operational aspects such as tasks, tool–workpiece interactions, and environmental factors that shape technical requirements (Dreher 2025).

Because of these different logics, the ontology is presented and discussed separately for customer and user scenarios in the following subsections.

4.4.1 User Scenario

The user scenario ontology captures the operational perspective of the angle grinder—how the tool is applied in real tasks and under which contextual conditions. Figure 28 presents the central structure of the domain concept layer used in this thesis. For the sake of clarity, and to avoid overcomplicating the figure, only one direction of each relation (i.e., without showing the corresponding inverse property) is labelled on the connecting lines—typically the semantically more intuitive one.

The model is implemented in Protégé and is built upon the principles of ASAM OpenXOntology and HQDM, while adopting the scenario structuring pattern from CAMEnto. We selected CAMEnto because of its clear advantages in representing contextual relationships between actors, devices, and environments in a structured and reusable way (see Section 2.3.3).

Accordingly, the relevant core classes from CAMEnto—*User*, *Device*, *Environment*, *Location*, *Time*, and *Activity*—were incorporated as the basis for our scenario ontology. Consistent with HQDM and OpenXOntology, the representation follows a triple-based logic (subject–predicate–object) and prefers entity-oriented modeling, meaning that important attributes and relations are represented as entities or classes, while numerical information is captured only through a generic has value property.

In practical terms, the ontology describes how a user, situated at a specific location, performs an activity. Each activity may involve certain devices, such as an angle grinder or protective equipment, and can act upon a workpiece, for instance, an aluminium rail. The location itself is characterised by environmental conditions, such as lighting, dust level, or the presence of flammable substances. Activities are temporally structured: they occur at a defined point in time, have a beginning and an end event, and can be sequenced so that one activity occurs before or after another. The subsequent subsections elaborate on these core elements step by step.

Figure 28: Domain ontology structure for user scenarios

Scenario

The *Scenario* class represents the overall system under investigation in this thesis, i.e., the complete configuration of user-related elements, activities, and contextual conditions. It functions as a container that aggregates all relevant components of a usage situation, including the user, the device, the workpiece, the location, and the associated environmental conditions.

In alignment with the HQDM core ontology, *Scenario* is mapped to the class *SystemState*. According to HQDM, systems are defined as “an organized or connected group of physical objects,” and a *SystemState* may represent either the whole life of the system or a temporal part of it. This correspondence reflects the intended role of the *Scenario* class: it provides a temporally bounded state of the socio-technical system “angle grinder in use,” capturing the entirety of its components and their relations at a given point in time.

Within the *Scenario*, two essential system components are defined: the *User* and the *Location*. Both are modelled as *WholeLifeSystemComponent* in HQDM and are linked to the scenario via the object property *hasComponent*. To reflect the fact that, at a given point in time, one scenario corresponds to exactly one operator at one workplace, the following cardinality constraints are applied:

- Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ User [1]
- Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ Location [1]

Domain Concept	Core Concept
Scenario	SystemState
User	WholeLifeSystemComponent
Location	WholeLifeSystemComponent

Table 10: Scenario and Mapping HQDM core concepts

User

The *User* class represents the human operator of the angle grinder within a scenario. Accordingly, it can be described both in relation to the overall *Scenario* and in relation to the *Activity* that is performed.

First, in relation to the *Scenario*, the user is defined as a system component:

- User $\xrightarrow{\text{componentOf}}$ Scenario [0:n]

Here, the relation `componentOf` is understood as the inverse of `hasComponent`. This reflects that a user may participate in multiple scenarios over time, while each scenario contains exactly one operator at a given point in time.

Second, in relation to the *Activity*, the user acts as the subject of the performed task:

- User $\xrightarrow{\text{participantOf}}$ Activity [1:n]

In this context, the user takes the role of a *Participant* within the *PhysicalObjectState*. The cardinality constraint [1:n] specifies that each user participates in at least one activity and may be involved in multiple activities, reflecting the possibility of a user carrying out different tasks across scenarios.

Furthermore, the *User* is characterised by multiple properties such as age, skill level, or occupational position. The relation between the *User* and its attributes is formally expressed as:

- User $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ UserProperty [1:n]

This indicates that a user can be associated with multiple user-related properties, each of which is represented as a dedicated entity. In line with HQDM modeling principles, these properties are not expressed as literal values but as entities, which enables them to carry additional semantics and to be reused across different contexts.

User Property

From the empirical database, several user-related factors were identified that have a direct influence on the execution of angle grinder scenarios. Table 11 summarises the selected user properties, their role in the domain ontology, and their mapping to HQDM core concepts.

Domain Concept	Core Concept
Age	PhysicalProperty
Disability	SetOfPhysicalObjectState
Training	SetOfPhysicalObjectState
Position	SetOfParticipant
ExperienceDuration	PhysicalProperty\Time

Table 11: User properties and their mapping to HQDM core concepts

The user properties are defined as follows:

- **Age:** the biological age of the user. It is mapped to a *PhysicalProperty*, since age is a measurable, continuous characteristic that directly influences the user's capability to operate the tool.
- **Disability:** indicates whether the user has physical or mental limitations that may affect the safe use of the angle grinder. It is modelled as a *SetOfPhysicalObjectState*, because disability is not a continuous property but rather a state condition of the user.
- **Training:** specifies whether the user has received relevant instruction or certification in handling angle grinders. It is also represented as a *SetOfPhysicalObjectState*, since training reflects a specific state of the user (trained or untrained) rather than a quantifiable property.
- **Position:** the occupational role of the user (e.g., worker, technician, supervisor). It is mapped to a *SetOfParticipant*, because position defines the user's role within the socio-technical system and links the user to functional responsibilities.
- **ExperienceDuration:** the length of time the user has been in contact with or actively using angle grinders. This is mapped to a *PhysicalProperty* with temporal dimension, since it represents a measurable, time-based characteristic of user experience.

Location

The *Location* class represents the physical workplace where the user operates the angle grinder. It is considered an integral part of the system, as the spatial context directly affects the execution of activities and the conditions under which the tool and workpiece are used. Accordingly, in the HQDM framework, *Location* is mapped to the core concept *WholeLifeSystemComponent*.

In the domain ontology, two main categories of workplace are distinguished:

- **Indoor:** enclosed environments such as workshops, factories, or garages, where environmental factors (e.g., lighting, ventilation, dust extraction) are typically controlled.
- **Outdoor:** open environments such as construction sites or fieldwork areas, where environmental influences (e.g., weather, temperature, humidity) are less controlled and more variable.

Similar to the treatment of driving environments in OpenXOntology, a location is associated with surrounding *EnvironmentalConditions*. These may include factors such as dust level, lighting, noise, or temperature. The ontology formalises this relation through the object property `hasEnvironmentalCondition`, with cardinality $[1 : n]$, since one location may have none, one, or several relevant environmental conditions at the same time. The relation is formally expressed as:

- Location $\xrightarrow{\text{hasEnvironmentalCondition}}$ Environmental Condition $[1:n]$

EnvironmentalCondition & EnvironmentalConditionProperty

The *EnvironmentalCondition* class represents the surrounding conditions of a *Location*. In analogy to OpenXOntology and in alignment with HQDM, these conditions are mapped to the core concept *PhysicalProperty* and are likewise encoded as entities.

The associated *EnvironmentalConditionProperty* classes specify measurable or categorical parameters of each condition. Numerical values are expressed via the generic property `has_value`.

The relationships are formalised as follows:

- EnvironmentalCondition $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ EnvironmentalConditionProperty $[0:n]$

It should be noted, however, that not all environmental conditions are characterized by explicit properties. For certain categories—such as *FlammableCondition*, *OverheadCondition*, or *WeatherCondition*—their specific characteristics are represented through dedicated subclasses rather than property values. For instance, *FlammableCondition* is subdivided into *FlammablePresent* and *FlammableAbsent*, thereby distinguishing whether flammable materials are present in the environment. Similarly, *OverheadCondition* is modeled through the subclasses *OverheadPresent* and *OverheadAbsent*, capturing the existence of overhead structures or obstacles. In contrast, *WeatherCondition* follows a categorical scheme with subclasses such as *Rainy*, *Sunny*, or *Snowy*, representing typical meteorological states. These subclass-based representations allow such conditions to be integrated consistently into the ontology without requiring additional numerical or property-based attributes.

Each type of *EnvironmentalCondition* captures a distinct aspect of the workplace:

- **ChemicalCondition:** presence of chemical agents in the environment.
- **ConnectivityCondition:** availability and stability of digital connectivity.

- **FlammableCondition:** Boolean condition indicating whether flammable materials are present.
- **HumidityCondition:** moisture level in the environment.
- **IlluminationCondition:** intensity and quality of lighting.
- **NoiseCondition:** background noise level during operation.
- **OverheadWorkCondition:** Boolean condition indicating whether the task is performed above head height.
- **ParticulatesCondition:** concentration of dust or airborne particles.
- **PowerStabilityCondition:** stability of electrical supply.
- **SparkCondition:** frequency of sparks occurring during operation.
- **TemperatureCondition:** ambient temperature range.
- **VentilationCondition:** effectiveness of air circulation.
- **VibrationCondition:** intensity of environmental or tool-related vibrations.
- **WeatherCondition:** categorical weather state (e.g., sunny, snowy, rainy).
- **WorkingHeightCondition:** numeric height at which the work is performed.

EnvironmentalCondition	EnvironmentalConditionProperty
ChemicalCondition	chemicalConcentration
ConnectivityCondition	bandwidth\latency
FlammableCondition	
HumidityCondition	relativeHumidity
IlluminationCondition	lightingIntensity
NoiseCondition	noiseLevel
OverheadWorkCondition	
ParticulatesCondition	particulateConcentration
PowerStabilityCondition	voltageStability
SparkCondition	sparkFrequency
TemperatureCondition	temperature
VentilationCondition	ventilationRate
VibrationCondition	vibrationLevel
WeatherCondition	
WorkingHeightCondition	height

Table 12: EnvironmentalConditions and their typical EnvironmentalConditionProperties

Activity

The *Activity* class captures the actions performed within a scenario. In HQDM and OpenX-Ontology, it is mapped to the core concept *ActivityState*, defined as “a state that represents the whole life of an activity or a temporal part of an activity. Activities consist of their participants, which are members of *PhysicalObjectState*, and cause some event. The end event of an activity state is caused by that activity, which implies that the activity describes some change between the start event and the end event.”

Accordingly, each activity is temporally bounded by a beginning and an ending event:

- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasBeginning}}$ Event/PointInTime [0:1]
- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasEnding}}$ Event/PointInTime [0:1]

Beyond temporal boundaries, activities can also be related to one another through sequencing properties such as:

- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{occursAfter/Before}}$ Activity [0:n]

These relations allow complex workflows to be represented as structured sequences of activity states.

In addition, activities may consist of smaller sub-activities through the relation *hasTemporalPart*, which allows the decomposition of complex tasks into finer-grained steps. For example, a *PreparationActivity* can contain the sub-activities *SafetyCheck* and *WearPPE*, which together form part of the preparation process:

- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasTemporalPart}}$ Activity [0:n]

The subclasses of *Activity* can be grouped into six main categories, each capturing a specific stage of tool operation:

- **OperationalActivity:** tasks that prepare or adjust the tool itself, such as changing or installing attachments.
- **ProcessingActivity:** core machining tasks that directly act on the workpiece, including cutting, grinding, or polishing.
- **ExecutionActivity:** the actual use of the angle grinder, including waiting states during operation.
- **PostProcessingActivity:** activities that follow tool use, such as cleaning or storing the device.

- **PreparationActivity:** steps taken before tool use, including fixing the workpiece, wearing PPE, or preparing the workplace.
- **SafetyActivity:** activities explicitly related to personal protection and safety checks.

Table 13 summarises these subclasses and their representative tasks. Among them, the **ProcessingActivity** is of particular importance because it directly links to the workpiece. This can be formally expressed as:

- ProcessingActivity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProcessingActivityObject}}$ Workpiece [0:1]

Subclass	Representative tasks
OperationalActivity	ChangeAttachment, InstallAttachment, RemoveAttachment, AdjustSpeed
ProcessingActivity	Cutting, Deburring, Engraving, Grinding, Polishing, Sanding, WeldingPreparation
ExecutionActivity	AngleGrinderOperation, Waiting
PostProcessingActivity	Clean, StoreDevice
PreparationActivity	FixWorkpiece, InstallAttachment, MountDisc, SelectAngleGrinder, SelectAttachment, WearPPE, EnsurePowerSupply, MarkMeasurement, MaskSurface, PrepareWorkplace, SafetyCheck
SafetyActivity	WearPPE, SafetyCheck

Table 13: Activity subclasses in the angle grinder domain

Workpiece & Workpiece Property

The *Workpiece* class represents the physical object that is directly processed by the angle grinder during an activity. In the HQDM framework, the workpiece can be mapped to both *WholeLifeSystemComponent* and *WholeLifeOrdinaryPhysicalObject*, reflecting its dual role as a system element and as a tangible physical entity.

The *WorkpieceProperty* class captures the measurable or categorical attributes of the workpiece, such as geometry, dimensions, or material characteristics. In HQDM, these are aligned with the core concept *PhysicalProperty*, which allows them to be represented as entities rather than literal values.

The relationship can be formally expressed as:

- Workpiece $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ workpieceProperty [1:n]

Table 14 summarises the main categories of workpiece properties:

WorkpieceProperty	Description
geometryShape	The overall geometric form of the workpiece (e.g., cylindrical, rectangular, irregular).
hardness	The material hardness, influencing machinability and tool wear.
heightQuantity	The vertical dimension of the workpiece.
lengthQuantity	The longitudinal dimension of the workpiece.
widthQuantity	The lateral dimension of the workpiece.
materialType	The type of material (e.g., steel, aluminium, wood, plastic).
surfaceCondition	The condition of the surface (e.g., rough, polished, coated).

Table 14: Workpiece properties and their corresponding physical characteristics

Device

The *Device* class represents the physical objects that are involved during an *Activity*. Formally, devices are linked to activities through the relation:

- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{involves}}$ Device [0:n]

For example, a *WearPPE* activity involves a *PersonalProtectionEquipment* device.

It should be noted, however, that not all activities necessarily involve a device. Certain activities, such as *SafetyCheck*, are primarily procedural or observational in nature and therefore do not require any physical device to be associated with them.

In the HQDM framework, devices can be mapped to both *WholeLifeOrdinaryPhysicalObject* and *WholeLifeSystemComponent*, as they simultaneously function as tangible objects and as components of the broader system under consideration.

Table 15 summarises the domain-specific subclasses of devices used in angle grinder scenarios:

Tool Component

The *ToolComponent* class represents the internal parts and functional modules of the angle grinder. In the HQDM framework, tool components are mapped to the core concept *WholeLifeSystemComponent*, highlighting their role as persistent elements that together constitute the system.

When the *AngleGrinder* is considered as the studied system, it is modelled as a *SystemState*, which can be decomposed into its constituent parts through the relation:

- AngleGrinder $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ ToolComponent [0:n]

Device (domain)	Description
AngleGrinder	The main power tool used in processing and execution activities.
ClampingTool	Tools used to fix or stabilise the workpiece (e.g., vise, clamps).
ExtractionAndChipCollection	Systems used to collect dust, chips, and debris during operation.
ExtractionHood	A protective hood guiding extraction of dust or sparks.
PersonalProtectionEquipment (PPE)	Safety equipment such as gloves, goggles, masks, or ear protection.
Workbench	The workplace surface where the workpiece is positioned and processed.

Table 15: Device subclasses in the angle grinder domain

The following subclasses of tool components were defined for the angle grinder domain:

ToolComponent	Description and Example
ControlComponent	components used to operate and control the basic functions of the angle grinder, including power activation, safety locks, and speed regulation.
DriveComponent	The power transmission parts, including motor and gearbox.
ErgonomicsFeatures	Components designed to improve handling and comfort (e.g., handle, grip surface).
SafetyFeatures	Built-in protective parts such as guards, emergency stop, or anti-kickback systems.
WorkingAttachment	Replaceable attachments used for specific processing tasks (e.g., cutting disc, grinding wheel, sanding pad).

Table 16: ToolComponent subclasses

4.4.2 Customer Scenario

While the user scenario ontology focuses on the operational use of the angle grinder in concrete tasks, the *customer scenario ontology* addresses the decision-making perspective that precedes tool operation. It captures how customers evaluate and compare products, how they prioritise between different properties, and how external influences shape the final decision. Figure 29 shows the central structure of this ontology: a scenario contains a *Customer* and may include a *SocialEnvironmentCondition*; The customer participates in decision-related activities, including considering various Physical/Social Properties of the angle grinder and assigning higher priority to certain aspects when trade-offs occur. For clarity, inverse object properties have not been depicted in the diagram, as in the user scenario ontology. For clarity, inverse object properties have not been depicted in the diagram, as in the user scenario ontology.

Unlike the user ontology, this domain concept layer was not derived from an existing reference model such as CAMEnto. Instead, it was inductively constructed from the empirical database, where recurring elements of customer behaviour and purchasing decisions were systematically summarised and abstracted into ontology classes and relations.

As in the user ontology, the model was implemented in Protégé and builds upon the core principles of ASAM OpenXOntology and HQDM, following a triple-based logic (subject–predicate–object) and an entity-oriented representation. The following subsections provide a detailed introduction to these elements.

Figure 29: Domain ontology structure for customer scenarios

In the customer ontology, the *Scenario* class retains the same foundational role as in the user ontology: it represents the overall system state that frames the situation under investigation. Formally, it is mapped to the HQDM core concept *SystemState*, which allows the scenario to be understood as the temporal configuration of all relevant system components.

While in the user scenario the central components were the *User* and the *Location*, the customer scenario shifts focus toward the *Customer* and the surrounding *SocialEnvironmentCondition*. Thus, the *Scenario* provides the structural container in which market-oriented decision-making processes take place.

- Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ Customer [1]
- Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasSocialEnvironmentCondition}}$ SocialEnvironmentCondition [1:n]

This mirrors the modeling logic of the user scenario, where Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ User/Location,

but adapts it to the decision-making context of customers by integrating social and institutional influences.

Customer

The Customer denotes the market actor who makes purchasing or adoption decisions regarding the angle grinder. Analogous to the modeling in the user scenario ontology, the Customer is represented in three complementary ways:

First, it is modelled as a *WholeLifeSystemComponent*, since it constitutes a persistent element of the scenario across its temporal span.

- Customer $\xrightarrow{\text{componentOf}}$ Scenario [0:n]

Second, when linked to decision-related activities, the Customer assumes the role of a *Participant*, analogous to the role of the user in operational activities.

- Customer $\xrightarrow{\text{participantOf}}$ Activity [1:n]

Third, the Customer is also the bearer of specific attributes, which capture relevant characteristics for decision making.

- Customer $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ CustomerProperty [1:n]

This modeling ensures that a customer may be associated with multiple scenario instances, while each scenario contains exactly one focal customer—mirroring the user ontology, where an operator is linked to the scenario at a given time. In this way, the Customer anchors the scenario to the market perspective, functions as a participant in decision-making activities, and is characterised by its own set of properties, thereby complementing the operational role of the User in the user scenario ontology.

Customer Property

From the empirical database, several key *CustomerProperties* were derived that strongly influence purchasing behaviour. By analogy with OpenXOntology, where *PhysicalProperty* is represented as a *SetOfState*, we introduced an additional class *SocialProperty* within the same modeling pattern. This extension allows socially constructed characteristics (e.g., brand trust, budget, organisational affiliation) to be represented in a structured way, consistent with the entity-oriented modeling principle of HQDM.

Table [17](#) shows the mapping of domain concepts to their corresponding HQDM core concepts.

The customer properties are defined as follows:

Table 17: Mapping of Customer Properties to HQDM Core Concepts

Domain Concept	Core Concept (HQDM)
Age	PhysicalProperty (SetOfState)
BrandTrust	SocialProperty (SetOfState)
Budget	SocialProperty (SetOfState)
ExperienceDuration	PhysicalProperty/Time (SetOfState)
Organisation	SocialProperty (SetOfState)
Position	SetOfParticipant

- **Age:** the biological age of the customer, categorised into ranges (e.g., 15–20 years, 21–29 years, etc.), represented as a *PhysicalProperty*.
- **BrandTrust:** preference or loyalty towards specific brands (e.g., Bosch, Einhell, Metabo), represented as a *SocialProperty*.
- **Budget:** the financial resources available for purchase decisions, represented as a *SocialProperty* since the concept of money is socially constructed.
- **ExperienceDuration:** the length of prior experience with angle grinders, modelled as a temporal *PhysicalProperty*.
- **Organisation:** the organisational context in which the customer is embedded (e.g., company, dealer, or private individual), captured as a *SocialProperty*.
- **Position:** the role of the customer within the procurement or usage process (e.g., individual buyer, dealer, or corporate buyer), represented as a *SetOfParticipant*.

Social Environment Condition & Social Environment Condition Property

In the user scenario ontology, the environment is represented through *PhysicalEnvironmentConditions* such as noise, dust, or lighting. By contrast, the customer scenario ontology focuses exclusively on the *social environment*, since purchasing decisions are primarily shaped by societal, regulatory, and economic influences. For this purpose, the class *SocialEnvironmentCondition* was introduced. Analogous to *EnvironmentalCondition* in OpenXOntology—which is modelled as a *PhysicalProperty*—the *SocialEnvironmentCondition* is represented here as a *SocialProperty*. This allows decision-relevant but non-physical factors, such as compliance with legal directives, supplier structures, or macro-economic trends, to be systematically captured within the ontology. The detailed classification of *SocialEnvironmentConditions* is presented in Table 18.

Among the three categories, only the *EconomicClimateCondition* is represented through explicit *SocialEnvironmentProperties* (e.g., GDP, PMI), which provide measurable indicators linked via `has_value`. In contrast, *LegalRegulation* and *SupplierRelationship* are modelled as predefined subclasses.

SocialEnvironmentCondition (domain)	Example
EconomicClimateCondition	Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Purchasing Managers' Index (PMI)
LegalRegulation	Machinery Directive, RoHS Directive, Low Voltage Directive, EMC Directive, Noise Emission Directive
SupplierRelationship	Tier 1, Tier 2, Tier 3 suppliers

Table 18: SocialEnvironmentConditions

- **EconomicClimateCondition:** represents the overall economic climate relevant to purchasing decisions. It is captured by *SocialEnvironmentProperties* such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Purchasing Managers' Index (PMI), which can be expressed numerically via `has_value`.
- **LegalRegulation:** represents the legal and regulatory framework within which a product must comply. It is modelled as subclasses with enumerated instances (e.g., Machinery Directive, RoHS Directive, Low Voltage Directive, EMC Directive, Noise Emission Directive), each defining specific compliance requirements.
- **SupplierRelationship:** represents the customer's structural relationship to suppliers. It is expressed as subclasses with categorical instances reflecting supplier hierarchy (e.g., Tier 1, Tier 2, Tier 3), which indicate proximity to the manufacturer and potential influence on procurement decisions.

Angle Grinder & Tool Component

The representation of the *AngleGrinder* and its associated *ToolComponents* in the customer scenario ontology directly follows the modeling approach already introduced in the user scenario ontology (see Section 4.4.1). In both cases, the *AngleGrinder* is treated as the central device, mapped to the HQDM core concepts *WholeLifeOrdinaryPhysicalObject* and *WholeLifeSystemComponent*. Its internal structure is described via the object property `hasComponent`, linking it to subclasses such as *ControlComponent*, *DriveComponent*, *ErgonomicsFeatures*, *SafetyFeatures*, and *WorkingAttachment*.

Physical & Social Property of Angle Grinder

In the customer scenario ontology, the characteristics of the *AngleGrinder* are divided into two categories: *PhysicalProperties* and *SocialProperties*. Consistent with the HQDM modeling principle, both are represented as subclasses of *SetOfState*. While *PhysicalProperties* describe measurable and technical aspects of the device, *SocialProperties* capture socially constructed but decision-relevant factors such as price, service, or leasing models.

Physical Properties

The following physical properties describe the measurable technical characteristics of the angle grinder:

- **EnergyConsumptionLevel:** indicates how much energy the angle grinder consumes during operation. This property directly reflects efficiency and is relevant for both cost calculation and sustainability considerations.
- **Ergonomics:** models the ergonomic quality of the tool's design and its impact on user posture and health. In the ontology, ergonomics are further specified by assessment standards such as REBA (Rapid Entire Body Assessment) and RULA (Rapid Upper Limb Assessment), which allow a structured evaluation of ergonomic risks.
- **MassQuantity:** the total physical mass of the device, which contributes to its robustness but may also influence portability.
- **PowerRating:** specifies the rated electrical power output of the grinder. This property determines the tool's capability to perform demanding tasks such as cutting thicker materials.
- **ProductLifespan:** represents the expected durability of the angle grinder across its life cycle. It provides customers with an estimation of how long the device can be used before replacement is required.
- **Weight:** captures the operational weight of the tool as experienced by the user during handling. Although closely related to mass, weight in practice affects usability, user fatigue, and suitability for prolonged tasks.

Social Properties.

Beyond measurable technical attributes, customer decision-making is also influenced by socially constructed aspects of the angle grinder. These are represented as *SocialProperties*, reflecting market, financial, and service-related considerations:

- **SystemCompatibility:** describes whether the grinder is compatible with a brand ecosystem, such as a shared battery system or modular tool platform. For instance, if a customer already owns multiple Bosch devices with interchangeable batteries, compatibility strongly increases the likelihood of selecting another Bosch angle grinder.
- **BusinessModels:** captures the availability of alternative financial acquisition options, such as leasing, rental, or subscription services. For example, corporate buyers may prefer leasing contracts to reduce upfront investment and to ensure regular replacement of tools.
- **OperatingCosts:** represents the recurring costs associated with using the tool, such as electricity consumption, replacement discs, or routine maintenance. A tool with a low

purchase price but high operating costs may, in the long run, be less attractive than a more expensive but efficient alternative.

- **OperationNeeds:** categorises the tool's suitability for different workload intensities. In the ontology, three levels are distinguished:
 - *HeavyDutyOperationNeeds* — e.g., continuous use in industrial metal fabrication.
 - *ModerateDutyOperationNeeds* — e.g., regular use in workshops or small businesses.
 - *LightDutyOperationNeeds* — e.g., occasional use by private individuals for DIY projects.
- **Price:** the monetary cost of acquiring the tool. For private buyers, price may be the dominant decision factor, whereas professional buyers often consider price in relation to service level, durability, and operating costs.
- **RepairService:** represents the warranty period length offered for the angle grinder. For example, some manufacturers provide a basic 12-month warranty, while others extend it to 24 or even 36 months depending on product registration. A longer warranty period reduces the perceived risk of purchase and can be a decisive factor in customer decision-making.
- **ServiceLevel:** captures the quality of after-sales service and customer support. In the ontology, this is categorised into levels such as α , β , and γ . For example:
 - *ServiceLevel* α : premium support including immediate replacement tools, 24/7 hotline, and on-site repair within 24 hours.
 - *ServiceLevel* β : standard manufacturer service such as email support, a repair turnaround of several days, and basic spare parts availability.
 - *ServiceLevel* γ : minimal support, limited to warranty claims and generic customer service with long response times.

Such distinctions help model how different customer groups (e.g., professional contractors vs. DIY users) perceive the value of service quality in their decision-making.

Activity

As in the user scenario ontology, an *Activity* in the customer ontology is modelled as an *ActivityState*. This means that activities are temporally bounded and can be described by their start and end events through the relations *hasBeginning* and *hasEnding*. Furthermore, customer activities may be decomposed into smaller sub-activities using *hasTemporalPart*, and their sequence can be expressed via the relations *occursAfter* and *occursBefore*. The *Customer* participates in these activities as the central decision-making actor.

- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasBeginning}}$ Event/PointInTime [0:1]
- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasEnding}}$ Event/PointInTime [0:1]

- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{occursAfter/Before}}$ Activity [0:n]
- Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasTemporalPart}}$ Activity [0:n]

To capture the different kinds of decision-oriented processes, three categories of customer activities are introduced:

NoObjectActivity

This category contains activities that do not directly act on a specific external object, but rather describe preparatory or organisational tasks that shape the decision-making process. They reflect information gathering, requirement definition, and administrative interactions that precede object-specific actions. Examples include:

- **AngleGrinderMarketResearch:** collecting information about different products, prices, and suppliers.
- **NeedsIdentification:** clarifying the requirements of the customer or organisation before making a purchase.
- **ContractPreparation:** drafting contractual agreements and procurement documents.
- **Negotiation:** engaging in discussions with suppliers to adjust terms and conditions.
- **RequestQuotes:** formally requesting quotations from different suppliers.
- **SubmitQuoteToAdministration:** submitting documentation for approval within an organisation.

Although these activities do not involve a direct object, they provide the structural and organisational foundation for subsequent purchasing decisions.

ObjectActivity

This category consists of activities in which the customer explicitly interacts with or evaluates an object. Such relations are captured through the property `hasActivityObject`, which connects the activity to the corresponding entity (product, component, or supplier). Typical examples include:

- **Consideration:** evaluating an *AngleGrinder* or one of its *Properties*.
 - Consideration $\xrightarrow{\text{hasActivityObject}}$ AngleGrinder/Property [0:n]
- **Purchasing:** executing the act of buying the *AngleGrinder* or a specific *ToolComponent*.

– Purchasing $\xrightarrow{\text{hasActivityObject}}$ AngleGrinder/ToolComponent [0:n]

- **SupplierPrequalification:** assessing a potential supplier to ensure compliance with required standards.

– SupplierPrequalification $\xrightarrow{\text{hasActivityObject}}$ Supplier [0:n]

By linking the activity to its object in this way, the ontology is able to represent not only the fact that an action takes place, but also what entity is affected or evaluated by the customer.

PriorityRelationAssertion.

A distinct group of activities concerns the explicit prioritisation of different product properties in the customer's decision-making process. Here, the ontology applies the modeling technique of *reification*, turning the priority relation itself into an entity that can be connected to both subject and object. The properties `hasPriorityRelationSubject` and `hasPriorityRelationObject` define the two compared attributes.

For example:

- Customer1 $\xrightarrow{\text{participantOf}}$ HigherPriorityAssertion
- HigherPriorityAssertion $\xrightarrow{\text{hasPriorityRelationSubject}}$ Property1
- HigherPriorityAssertion $\xrightarrow{\text{hasPriorityRelationObject}}$ Property2

This enables the ontology to explicitly state that, for *Customer1*, *Property1* has a higher priority than *Property2*.

In the same way, two additional relations are modelled:

- **LowerPriorityAssertion:** expresses that one property is explicitly less important than another for a given customer.
- **SamePriorityAssertion:** expresses that two properties are considered equally important by the customer.

Together, these three types of assertions (*HigherPriorityAssertion*, *LowerPriorityAssertion*, and *SamePriorityAssertion*) allow the ontology to capture customer-specific preference hierarchies in a structured and queryable way. Such modeling enables systematic analysis of trade-offs and decision factors in customer scenarios.

4.4.3 Instance Construction Pipeline (from scenario text to Protégé)

In order to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed ontology, we introduce an *Instance Construction Pipeline* that systematically transforms empirical scenario data into machine-readable instances in Protégé. The purpose of this pipeline is to provide a transparent and reproducible procedure for moving from raw qualitative inputs—such as interviews, workshops, or surveys—to structured ontology-based representations. The pipeline ensures that empirical findings are consistently captured, classified according to the ontology structure, and implemented as individuals with explicit relations between entities. To illustrate this procedure, we use an example derived from the interview dataset. A raw user scenario description obtained from an interview is taken as input. Through the steps of the pipeline, shown in Figure 30, the scenario is first extracted in its original form, then mapped to the ontology classes and properties, transformed into a concise descriptive narrative, and finally implemented as an instance in Protégé. This example serves both as a proof-of-concept for the modeling method and as a reference for constructing further instances in a systematic way.

Figure 30: Instance Construction Pipeline

Step1: Raw Scenario Data Extraction

The first step consists of collecting the original scenario description as provided by the interview participant. In this case, the scenario concerns the shortening of roller shutters. The participant describes the sequence of actions as follows:

“Arrival at the warehouse, where all batteries (all from Würth) are fully charged and ready on the charging station. The roller shutters need to be shortened. Mark the dimensions, the cutting disc is already mounted since this is a regular task. Insert the battery, fix the material in a suitable place (considering the direction of sparks and comfortable working height, the task is performed alone), put on protective equipment (glasses, hearing protection, gloves), cut the U-shape aluminum profiles (separation), clean the device after it has cooled down.”

In addition to the activity description, background information on the user was collected: the participant belongs to the age group 21–29 years, holds a secondary school degree with completed carpenter training and additional technical courses, and works in a small family-run company (father and son) engaged in installation and trade of building components within a 150 km radius in the border region between Germany, Switzerland, and France. The participant has 5–10 years of professional experience in this context.

Step2: Ontology-based Classification and Mapping

In the second step, the raw scenario description is systematically structured by classifying its content according to the ontology. As introduced in Section 4.4.1, the relevant domain classes include *User & User Property*, *Location*, *Environmental Condition & Environmental Condition Property*, *Activity*, *Workpiece*, *Device*, and *Tool Component*. The elements of the scenario description presented in the previous step are mapped to these classes as follows:

User & User Property

The first table illustrates the mapping of the interview data to the ontology classes *User* and *User Property*. In this representation, the individual *User* (Jeremy Schäfer) is linked to the corresponding *User Property* instances via the object property *hasProperty*, expressed as:

$$\text{User} \xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}} \text{UserProperty.}$$

Domain Class	Subclass	Value (Instance)
User		Jeremy Schäfer
User Property	Age Group	21–29 years
	Disability Condition	No Disability
	Training	Trained
	Experience Duration	5–10 years

Table 19: Mapping of User and User properties

Location& Environmental Condition

In the ontology, the working place described in the interview corresponds to a *Warehouse*, which is classified as an *Indoor Location*. In addition, three specific *Environmental Conditions* were identified from the scenario description. They are linked to the scenario through the object property *hasEnvironmentCondition*, as listed in Table 20.

Domain Class	Subclass	Value (Instance)
Location	Indoor Location	Warehouse
EnvironmentCondition	Flammable Condition	FlammableAbsent
	Overhead Work Condition	OverheadWorkAbsent
	Working Height Condition	WorkHeight01(1m)

Table 20: Mapping of Location and Environmental Conditions

Workpiece

The scenario involves the processing of a specific *Workpiece*. In this case, the relevant workpiece corresponds to an aluminium profile with a U-shaped cross-section. Within the ontology, such information is represented as an individual of the class *Workpiece*, which is connected to its material and geometrical characteristics through the object property *hasProperty*, as summarised in Table 21.

Domain Class	Subclass	Value (Instance)
Workpiece		Roller shuttle (profile)
Workpiece Property	Material type	Aluminum
	Geometry shape	U_shape

Table 21: Mapping of Workpiece and its properties

Device& Tool Component

The scenario further specifies the use of a *Device*, namely an angle grinder. Within the ontology, the angle grinder is represented as an individual of the class *Device*, and it is linked to its specific properties and tool components. In this case, the angle grinder has the property *model Würth* and is associated with two tool components: the cutting disc and the battery. In addition to the primary device, the participant also mentioned protective equipment such as safety glasses, hearing protection, and gloves. The mapping is summarised in Table 22.

Domain Class	Subclass	Value (Instance)
Device	Angle grinder	Angle grinder
AngleGrinderProperty	Model	Würth
Tool Component	Attachment	Cutting disc
Tool Component	Drive Component	Battery
Device	Protective Equipment	Safety glasses
		Hearing protection
		Gloves

Table 22: Mapping of Device, Tool Component

Activity

The sequence of actions described in the interview can be structured into three activity groups: *PreparationActivity*, *ProcessingActivity*, and *PostProcessingActivity*. Each group contains individual activities, which are represented in the ontology as instances of the class *Activity* and connected to the overall scenario through temporal relations. The mappings are summarised in the following tables.

Table 23 represents the set of *Preparation Activities* identified in the scenario. These activities capture the sequence of actions that must be completed before the actual cutting operation

can begin. The process starts with *Arriving at the warehouse*, which marks the beginning of the preparation phase. It then continues with tasks such as *Preparing the workplace*, *Marking the measurement*, and *Ensuring the power supply*. Further preparation steps include *Mounting* and *Wearing* personal protective equipment. Both activities are explicitly linked to corresponding entities via the relation *involves*: *Mounting* involves the *Workpiece*, as the material must be fixed in a suitable position before cutting, while *Wear* involves the protective equipment (safety glasses, hearing protection, and gloves). The preparation phase concludes with the activity *Angle Grinder On*, which represents the transition point to the processing activity.

Domain Class	Object Property	Value (Instance)
PreparationActivity	hasBeginning	Arriving_at_the_warehouse
	hasTemporalPart	Prepare_the_workplace
	hasTemporalPart	Mark_the_measurement
	hasTemporalPart	Ensure_the_power_supply
	hasTemporalPart	Mounting (Workpiece)
	hasTemporalPart	Wear (PPE)
	hasEnding	Angle_Grinder_On

Table 23: Preparation activities mapped to ontology

Table 24 represents the *Processing Activity* at the core of the scenario. The activity *Cutting* is modelled as the central operation, which begins once the angle grinder has been switched on and ends when the tool is switched off. The target object or workpiece of this processing activity is explicitly identified as the *Roller shutter*, represented through the property *hasProcessingActivityObject*.

Domain Class	Object Property	Value (Instance)
ProcessingActivity		Cutting
	hasBeginning	Angle_Grinder_On
	hasProcessingActivityObject	Roller shutter
	hasEnding	Angle_Grinder_Off

Table 24: Processing Activity mapped to ontology

Table 25 summarises the *Post-processing Activities* that follow the cutting operation. This phase begins once the device has sufficiently cooled down, which is represented through the property. Two subsequent activities are identified as temporal parts of this phase: *Clean*, which refers to removing dust and residues from the tool to ensure durability, and *Store device*, which describes returning the angle grinder to its designated storage place.

Domain Class	Object Property	Value (Instance)
PostprocessingActivity	hasBeginning	The_device_is_cooled_down
	hasTemporalPart	Clean
	hasTemporalPart	Store_device

Table 25: Post-processing activities mapped to ontology

Step3: Descriptive Narrative

Based on the structured classification of entities and activities in Step 2, the scenario can now be transformed into a human-readable descriptive narrative. This narrative consolidates the identified classes—such as *User*, *Workpiece*, *Device*, *Tool Component*, *Environmental Condition*, and the three groups of *Activities*—into a coherent text representation.

In the present case, the descriptive narrative reads as follows:

A trained carpenter (age 21–29, 5–10 years of professional experience) performs the task of shortening roller shutters in an indoor warehouse environment.

The workpiece is an aluminium profile with a U-shaped, which is fixed in place before processing.

The device used is an angle grinder (model Würth) equipped with a cutting disc and powered by a battery.

The preparation phase involves arriving at the workplace, preparing the workstation, marking the measurements, fixing the material, mounting the workpiece, and wearing personal protective equipment (safety glasses, hearing protection, gloves).

The processing phase consists of cutting the aluminium roller shutter with the angle grinder.

Finally, in the post-processing phase, the tool is allowed to cool down, cleaned and stored back.

Step4: Implementation in Protégé

In the final step, the classified scenario elements and descriptive narrative are implemented as ontology instances in Protégé. For this scenario, individuals were manually created for each relevant class (*User*, *Workpiece*, *Device*, *Tool Component*, *Activity*, *Location* and *EnvironmentalCondition*).

After all relevant individuals had been instantiated, the ontology content could be exported and processed outside of Protégé. For instance, the *CSV Export* plugin enables the extraction of individuals and their relations into a tabular format, which can be further analysed in spreadsheet software or imported into other modeling tools (Figure 31).

Entity	participantOf	hasProcessingActivityObject	hasTemporalPart	hasProperty
Jeremy_Schäfer	'Preparation_activity_01' 'cut' 'PostProcessingActivity'			'AgeGroup2' 'Mid_level_Experience' 'Trained' 'NoDisability'
Preparation_activity_01			'Wear' 'Mounting' 'Prepare_the_workplace' 'Mark_the_measurement' 'Ensure_the_power_supply' 'Select'	
cut		'roller_shutter'		
PostProcessingActivity			'Store_device' 'Clean'	
roller_shutter				'Aluminum' 'U_shape'

Figure 31: Ontology content exported via Protégé CSV-Export

Complementary to this tabular exploration, the overall structure of the scenario can also be inspected and verified directly in Protégé. The OntoGraph plugin was used to visualise the resulting network of entities and their relations, as illustrated in Figure 32

Figure 32: Scenario instance represented in Protégé OntoGraph

In addition, Protégé offers reasoning and querying capabilities that support the systematic analysis of scenario data. The *DL Query* interface, introduced in Section 2.5.2.2, for example, allows the specification of class expressions to retrieve instances that meet multiple conditions. To identify all scenarios that occur in a warehouse and explicitly include the environmental condition *FlammableAbsent*, the following query was formulated:

```
Scenario and (hasComponent value Warehouse)
and (hasComponent some (hasEnvironmentalCondition value FlammableAbsent))
```

Executing this query returned the example scenario instance, confirming that it is classified as taking place in a warehouse with the absence of flammable conditions (Figure 33). This demonstrates how DL Queries can combine structural and contextual constraints to extract meaningful subsets of scenarios within the ontology.

Figure 33: DL Query retrieving scenario instances

Finally, the ontology model can be exported into machine-readable formats such as *.owl*, *.ttl*, or *.json*. These formats enable seamless integration with external programming environments

(e.g., Java, Python), where the ontology can be queried, extended, or embedded into larger software pipelines. This ensures that the developed ontology is not limited to conceptual representation within Protégé, but can serve as a practical foundation for automated reasoning, simulation, and decision-support applications.

4.5 Proposed Validation Process

Building on the methodological reference from EnhanCE modeling (see Section 3.3.3), the validation of the proposed ontology-based scenario modeling method will follow a hypothesis-driven, experimentally controlled procedure. Three hypotheses are formulated, each addressing a different aspect of how participants describe customer and user scenarios when supported by the modeling method:

H1 (Coverage): Training with the ontology-based scenario modeling method will increase the *breadth* of scenario descriptions. Participants are expected to mention a wider variety of elements (e.g., activities, devices, environments) compared to working without training.

H2 (Detail): Training will increase the *level of detail* in scenario descriptions. Participants are expected to provide more specific and fine-grained information (e.g., concrete activities, tool characteristics, environmental conditions) rather than general or superficial statements.

H3 (Connectivity): Training will improve the *expression of relations* between scenario elements. Participants are expected to describe more connections and to form more coherent scenario narratives after training.

To test these hypotheses, a before-and-after experimental design is proposed, illustrated in Figure 34. Participants will be randomly assigned to two groups (A and B). Each group will describe customer and user scenarios for two technical systems: an *angle grinder* (System S1) and a more general *power tool* (System S2).

Figure 34: Proposed validation process for ontology-based scenario modeling

The procedure will consist of four consecutive phases:

1. **Introduction.** Participants will be introduced to the study procedure and assigned to groups A and B.
2. **Control phase.** Each group will first describe one system without training, relying solely on prior knowledge and intuition. This will provide a baseline for scenario descriptions. Group A will start with System S1 (angle grinder), while Group B will start with System S2 (power tool).
3. **Training phase.** All participants will receive structured training in the ontology-based modeling method, including key concepts, the entity structure, and illustrative examples implemented in Protégé.
4. **Test phase.** After training, groups will exchange systems and repeat the description tasks, this time explicitly applying the modeling method. By alternating systems, sequence effects and product-specific bias will be reduced.

System understanding will then be evaluated against the three hypotheses. For H1 (Coverage), the breadth of scenario descriptions will be measured by counting the number of distinct elements mentioned, classified into ontology categories (activities, tools, environments, etc.).

For H2 (Detail), two complementary indicators will be used: (a) the specificity of descriptions, rated on a three-point scale (1 = general, 2 = moderately detailed, 3 = highly specific); and (b) the number of fine-grained attributes mentioned (e.g., concrete activities, tool features, environmental conditions).

For H3 (Connectivity), the articulation of relations will be assessed by analysing (a) the number of explicit links described (e.g., user–activity, activity–tool, tool–environment), (b) the diversity of relation types covered, and (c) the coherence of relations, rated on a three-point scale (0 = isolated mentions, 1 = partial chains, 2 = coherent chains).

In addition to these primary indices, secondary measures such as task completion time, self-reported confidence, and usability ratings (System Usability Scale) will also be included to provide further insights into the practical value of the modeling method.

5 Discussion

This chapter provides a reflective discussion of the research findings and the ontology-based scenario model developed in this thesis. While the *Results* chapter (Section 4) presented the outcomes of the literature review, empirical analysis, applicability assessment, and ontology construction, the present discussion goes one step further by interpreting these outcomes in light of the research goals and questions introduced in Section 3.1.

The discussion is structured around three main perspectives.

First, it examines how the proposed ontology can be used as an instrument for the systematic identification of improvement requirements and reuse potentials in the context of power tools, thereby addressing the practical relevance of the model (Section 5.1).

Second, it provides a balanced evaluation of the ontology by highlighting its main strengths as well as its current limitations (Section 5.2).

Third, it outlines areas for improvement in the research design and development process (Section 5.3), identifying methodological refinements and extensions that could enhance robustness, reduce subjectivity, and broaden applicability in future work.

Together, these perspectives allow a comprehensive assessment of both the contributions and the boundaries of the present work. They demonstrate that while the ontology already provides a valuable foundation for structuring and analysing customer and user scenarios, further refinements and empirical validation are required to unlock its full potential as a reusable, industry-relevant knowledge model.

5.1 Ontology-driven Identification of Improvement Requirements and Reuse Potentials

A central objective of the ontology developed in this thesis was not only to formalise customer and user scenarios but also to support the systematic identification of improvement requirements and reuse potentials, as formulated in the research goal (Section 3.1.2). The ontology provides a structured, machine-readable representation of scenario elements (users, activities, devices, tool components, workpieces, environments) and their interrelations. This enables a range of ontology-driven analysis techniques that go beyond static documentation and can generate actionable insights for product development in the context of CG-Reman.

5.1.1 DL Query-based Screening

As demonstrated in Section 4.4.4 and introduced in Section 2.5.2.2, DL Queries provide a powerful means to retrieve scenario instances that satisfy multiple structural and contextual conditions simultaneously. Rather than examining scenarios in isolation, DL Queries enable the systematic filtering of the ontology to surface specific constellations of factors that are particularly relevant for product improvement. For example, queries combining conditions

such as *indoor environment*, *high dust exposure*, and *cutting activity* allow the automatic identification of scenarios where dust management is most critical.

By aggregating and analysing the results of such queries across the empirical database, recurrent patterns—or “problem constellations”—can be revealed. These patterns highlight the scenarios that occur most frequently in practice, thereby pointing to the most pressing user challenges. Frequency analysis of retrieved instances makes it possible to distinguish between isolated issues and systematic weaknesses that cut across multiple usage contexts.

The insights gained from this process can be directly translated into *high-priority improvement requirements*. For instance, if queries consistently retrieve scenarios characterised by *indoor + high dust + cutting*, this signals the need for improved dust extraction systems and enhanced sealing of components. Similarly, recurring combinations of *extended duration + overhead posture* would underline ergonomic requirements, such as reduced tool weight or improved handle design. In this way, DL Query analysis not only supports the detection of critical weaknesses but also provides a transparent evidence base linking scenario data to specific design implications.

5.1.2 Rule-based Annotation

Another way to support the identification of improvement requirements is through rule languages such as SWRL, introduced in Section 2.5.2.4. Unlike DL Queries, which only retrieve existing information, SWRL allows expert knowledge to be encoded in the form of if-then rules. These rules automatically annotate ontology instances whenever specific constellations of conditions are met.

The Figure [35](#) illustrates a simple example with the rule *DangerousCondition*. It specifies that if a scenario has an environmental condition where something flammable is present, the system automatically marks this scenario as dangerous.

This principle can be extended to derive improvement requirements. For example: – If a scenario involves high dust, indoor conditions, and cutting, then the ontology generates a requirement for improved dust extraction. – If there is high noise combined with prolonged use, then improved hearing protection is suggested. – If overhead work is carried out with a heavy device, then ergonomic redesign is recommended.

In this way, SWRL rules embed expert knowledge directly into the ontology. Scenarios are not only stored and retrieved but also actively evaluated: recurring risks or inefficiencies are automatically highlighted, and concrete improvement requirements are proposed. As the rule set expands, the ontology evolves into a semi-automated assessment tool that supports continuous product improvement and reuse potential assessment across generations.

Figure 35: SWRL rule *DangerousCondition* in Protégé.

5.2 Strengths and Limitations of the Proposed Ontology Model

The ontology-based scenario model developed in Section 4.4 represents the core contribution of this thesis. While its construction demonstrates the feasibility of applying ontology principles to capture both customer and user perspectives, a balanced assessment is necessary to understand the model's broader value and its current shortcomings. On the one hand, the ontology shows clear strengths in terms of extensibility, logical consistency, generalisability, and machine-readability. On the other hand, it also faces challenges, including complexity of use, the data-intensive nature of its construction, domain specificity, and limited validation.

This subsection provides a structured discussion of these aspects, highlighting both the contributions and constraints of the proposed model, and thereby outlining directions for refinement in future research.

5.2.1 Strengths

The proposed ontology-based scenario model demonstrates several strengths that enhance its value as both a conceptual framework and a practical tool. First, it offers *extensibility*, allowing new concepts, subclasses, and relations to be added without disrupting its internal logic. Second, its entity-oriented structure ensures *consistency and logical soundness*, making it suitable for reasoning and automated validation. Third, the modeling approach provides *potential generalisability*, since the dual perspective of users and customers can be applied to a wide range of products beyond the angle grinder case. Finally, the model's implementation in OWL ensures *machine-readability and queryability*, enabling targeted knowledge retrieval and integration with digital engineering tools.

The following subsections discuss each of these strengths in detail.

Extensibility

A central strength of the proposed ontology is its extensibility. This flexibility is rooted in the HQDM framework, which provides a stable set of core concepts while allowing domain-specific specialisation.

First, new *DomainConcepts* can be introduced on top of the existing layer. For example, beyond the current core classes of *Device*, *ToolComponent*, *User*, *Location*, and *Workpiece*, additional high-level concepts such as *SupportEquipment* (e.g., clamps, benches, safety shields) or *Material* (representing consumables beyond the workpiece itself) could be added if required by future scenarios. This ensures that the ontology remains open to new domains of knowledge without disrupting its internal logic.

Second, existing domain concepts can be refined by introducing further subclasses. For instance, the class *Device* can be subdivided into *PowerTool*, *MeasurementTool*, or *Auxiliary-Device*, while *Workpiece* could be specialised into *MetalWorkpiece*, *WoodWorkpiece*, or *CompositeWorkpiece*. This hierarchical refinement allows for increasingly detailed modeling while preserving consistency with the upper structure.

Third, the set of object properties connecting entities can be extended. If new interactions become relevant, additional relations can be defined—for example, connecting *Device* to *MaintenanceActivity* via the property *requiresMaintenance*. In this way, evolving practices and dependencies can be captured without reworking the ontology's foundations.

Finally, HQDM's principle of representing most important features as entities rather than literal values ensures extensibility at the entity level. Entities can be modified, extended, or replaced as empirical knowledge grows. For instance, the current representation of ergonomic assessment via REBA and RULA could be expanded to include other international standards or newly developed evaluation methods, without altering the surrounding structure.

Together, these mechanisms—extendable domain concepts, subclass refinement, expandable object properties, and entity-level flexibility—make the ontology a dynamic knowledge framework. It can evolve in step with technological innovation, empirical findings, and changing industrial requirements, rather than remaining a static artefact.

Consistency and Logical Soundness

A second advantage lies in its consistency and logical soundness. By following an entity-oriented approach, most relevant attributes are represented as classes and relations, rather than being reduced to literal values. This ensures that even characteristics traditionally expressed as numerical or string values—such as age, training level, or warranty period—are formalised as entities that can be explicitly connected to other concepts. As a result, the ontology becomes semantically richer and avoids the ambiguity that often arises when properties are encoded merely as unstructured data.

This modeling principle also supports automated reasoning. Tools such as the HerMiT reasoner or DL queries in Protégé can be applied to check the logical coherence of the ontology, ensuring that no contradictory class memberships or invalid property assertions occur. In addition, reasoning enables inference of hidden relations—for instance, if an activity involves a device and the device has a specific safety feature, the reasoner can infer that the activity inherits

safety-related conditions. Such consistency checking not only guarantees internal correctness but also improves reusability. When the ontology is extended with new concepts or applied in new domains, automated reasoning ensures that additions do not disrupt the logical structure.

Potential Generalisability

Another strength is the potential generalisability of the modeling logic, which can be understood in two dimensions.

First, the ontology is transferable across industrial domains. Although the case study focuses on the angle grinder, the scenario-based structuring—linking users, customers, activities, properties, and system components—can be readily applied to other technical products. For instance, similar ontologies could be developed for drilling machines, power saws, welding equipment, or even larger industrial systems such as CNC machining centres. In each case, the overall structure of scenarios, participants, activities, and contextual conditions remains valid, while only the domain-specific subclasses (e.g., tool components, workpiece types) require adaptation.

Second, the methodological approach of modeling both *user* and *customer* scenarios provides a generalisable framework for requirements analysis. By capturing the operational context (user perspective) alongside purchasing and decision-making factors (customer perspective), the ontology enables a holistic representation of system requirements. This dual-perspective modeling is not limited to power tools but can be applied to other products and services where technical feasibility and market acceptance must be evaluated together

Machine-readability and Queryability

The ontology also provides strong advantages in terms of machine-readability and queryability.

Implemented in OWL, it can be processed by ontology editors such as Protégé as well as by external applications and reasoning frameworks. This machine-readable foundation enables the ontology to act not only as a conceptual model but also as an operational knowledge base.

The Protégé supports DL Query and SPARQL queries, as illustrated in Section 4.4.3, which allow highly targeted retrieval of knowledge. For example, a DL query can be used to identify all scenarios where the workpiece material is aluminium, or where the location is classified as a workshop and the environmental condition includes high dust exposure. Such capabilities go beyond static modeling and enable dynamic exploration of the ontology contents.

In addition, the ontology can be exported into multiple machine-readable formats such as `.owl`, `.ttl`, and `.json`, ensuring interoperability with a wide range of digital tools. This makes the ontology possible for integration with simulation environments, digital twin platforms, and programming languages such as Java or Python. For instance, exported scenario data could be used to automatically generate simulation test cases or to feed into decision-support algorithms that assess component reuse feasibility.

5.2.2 Limitations

Despite its contributions, the proposed ontology-based scenario model also faces several limitations that constrain its immediate applicability and highlight areas for future improvement. First, the model introduces a high degree of *complexity*, requiring familiarity with ontology engineering concepts and specialized tools such as Protégé. Second, it is *data-intensive*, relying on extensive empirical input from workshops, surveys, and interviews, which may not always be feasible in industrial practice. Third, its current *domain specificity* ties the model closely to the angle grinder case, reducing direct transferability to other product families without significant adaptation. Finally, the ontology suffers from *limited validation*, as the proposed evaluation approach was not fully implemented and real-world industrial testing remains absent.

The following subsections discuss each of these limitations in detail.

Complexity

The first limitation of the proposed model lies in its complexity. With a large number of classes, relations, and constraints, the ontology requires familiarity with knowledge-modeling concepts to be fully understood. For practitioners who are not trained in ontology engineering, this complexity may act as a barrier to adoption.

Unlike conventional modeling tools, ontologies require users to understand abstract notions such as class hierarchies, object properties, and reasoning mechanisms. This learning curve is further amplified by the need to become proficient in ontology editors such as Protégé, which—despite being the de facto standard—demands significant training and practice. Although supporting tools such as OntoGraph or CSV export can simplify visualisation by offering more intuitive representations of the model, additional effort is still required to lower the entry barrier for industrial stakeholders.

Data-intensiveness

Another limitation is its data-intensiveness. Constructing the ontology required significant empirical input, including expert workshops, structured surveys, semi-structured interviews, and supplementary online data sources. Each of these activities is resource-demanding, both in terms of time and cost, and relies on sustained access to knowledgeable participants. In fast-paced industrial contexts, where time and personnel are often limited, such extensive data collection processes may not always be feasible. Furthermore, the accuracy and completeness of the ontology are strongly dependent on the quality of the collected data. If certain perspectives are underrepresented—for example, if only experienced users are consulted while novice users are excluded—the ontology may fail to capture the full diversity of real-world scenarios.

Biases in data collection, such as over-reliance on specific market regions or a limited set of customer types, can similarly distort the model.

Thus, while empirical grounding is essential for relevance and validity, it also increases the workload and places limits on the scalability of the approach.

Domain Specificity

The domain specificity of the model also limits its direct transferability. Although the underlying modeling logic is general, the current ontology is explicitly tailored to the angle grinder. Many of its classes and properties—such as cutting discs, PPE requirements, or grinder-specific ergonomic risks—are highly specialised for this tool family. Applying the ontology to other products would therefore require additional adaptation, which may involve restructuring parts of the domain layer, redefining activities, and introducing new entities. For example, transferring the model to a drilling machine would require replacing grinding-specific tool components with drilling bits and chucks, redefining the typical activities from cutting to drilling operations, and adjusting environmental conditions to reflect dust types and vibration profiles specific to drilling. This adaptation effort reduces the immediate reusability of the ontology outside the studied context and highlights the trade-off between precision and flexibility.

On the one hand, domain specificity ensures that the ontology accurately captures the details of the angle grinder use case; on the other hand, it constrains the model's direct applicability in broader industrial contexts without additional work. Thus, while the conceptual structure is generalisable, the current instantiation is domain-bound, requiring future research to develop reusable templates or reference ontologies that ease cross-domain transfer.

Limited Validation

Finally, the model faces the challenges of limited validation. Within the scope of this thesis, a validation approach was proposed—drawing on empirical instances and reasoning-based checks—but it was not implemented in practice. This absence of actual execution already represents a first shortcoming, as the model's applicability could not be demonstrated beyond conceptual design.

A second limitation arises from the lack of real-world industrial validation. While small-scale internal case studies were used to illustrate the ontology, the model has not yet been tested in operational engineering workflows or industrial decision-making contexts. Consequently, its usability, robustness, and potential benefits under practical conditions remain unverified. Future work will need to address both aspects: implementing the proposed validation approach in full and extending it into pilot projects within industry.

5.3 Areas for Improvements

As this work represents an initial exploration into ontology-based scenario modeling, it naturally comes with certain limitations and aspects that could be further refined. The ontology and its empirical foundations provide a useful starting point, but several areas for improvement can be identified. Addressing these would strengthen the robustness of the model and broaden its applicability in both research and industrial contexts.

5.3.1 Literature Review Procedure (Section 3.3.1.1)

The literature review provided a structured overview but can also be improved.

The current search strategy focused on a narrow set of scenario modeling keywords, which may have excluded relevant contributions using alternative terminology (e.g., “scenario planning”, “use case modeling”, “scenario analysis”). Future reviews should therefore expand the set of search terms to cover a broader range of scenario approaches.

Furthermore, while four major databases (Scopus, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, Web of Science) were consulted, additional sources such as ACM Digital Library, SpringerLink, or even Google Scholar could extend coverage.

It would also be valuable to include scenario modeling methods from adjacent disciplines such as strategic management, human–computer interaction, or organisational studies, which may offer transferable insights for engineering contexts.

Another limitation is that the review placed a strong emphasis on ontology-based approaches. While this aligns with the research focus, it risks overlooking valuable scenario modeling methods that are not explicitly ontology-driven but could nonetheless be adapted into an ontological representation. Including such methods in future reviews would allow a more comprehensive mapping of the scenario modeling landscape and help position ontology-based modeling within the broader methodological spectrum.

5.3.2 Empirical Database (Section 3.3.1.2 and Section 4.2)

Another area for improvement concerns the empirical database that underpins the ontology.

Although workshops, surveys, interviews, and supplementary online sources were used to collect scenario data, the overall dataset remains relatively limited in size. A larger and more diverse dataset would increase the representativeness of the captured scenarios and reduce the risk of bias introduced by small sample sizes.

In addition to quantity, the quality of the empirical data could also be improved. Some survey responses were brief or incomplete, while interview inputs varied in depth and level of detail. Future studies should therefore aim to involve a broader and more diverse set of participants, not only expanding the sample size but also including more professional users and industry experts. Their specialised knowledge would enrich the dataset with more precise descriptions of activities, environmental conditions, and decision-making factors, thereby improving both the reliability and the practical relevance of the ontology.

5.3.3 Ontology Development Process (Section 3.3)

The ontology development process in this work relied on manual modeling in Protégé, guided by established frameworks such as HQDM and CAMEOnto. While this ensured conceptual coherence and adherence to best practices, the crucial step of mapping empirical data into ontology concepts was performed largely through researcher interpretation. This introduces an element of subjectivity, as different researchers might classify or abstract scenario elements in varying ways.

Future improvements could address this limitation in several directions. First, introducing a more systematic coding scheme for data extraction—e.g., using qualitative data analysis tools such as NVivo or MAXQDA—would make the mapping process more transparent and reproducible. Second, involving multiple coders and calculating inter-coder reliability would reduce individual bias and increase the robustness of the ontology structure. Third, semi-automated ontology learning techniques, such as natural language processing (NLP) for term extraction or clustering, could complement manual modeling by suggesting candidate concepts and relations from the empirical dataset.

By reducing subjectivity and introducing more transparent procedures, future ontology development efforts could strengthen the reliability, scalability of the proposed modeling approach.

6 Summary and Outlook

This chapter concludes the thesis by summarising the key results and reflecting on their implications.

In the Summary section, the four research questions formulated in Section 3.1.2 are revisited, and concise answers are provided based on the findings presented in Chapter 4 and the discussion in Chapter 5.

Building on this foundation, the Outlook section formulates recommendations for further refinement and validation of the proposed model, as well as broader directions for future research.

6.1 Summary

The research questions were addressed in this thesis both in the results presented in Chapter 4 and in the discussion in Chapter 5, as summarised in Table 26.

Research Question	Chapter
1: Are there existing scenario modeling methods, particularly ontology-based approaches, that explicitly address customer and user perspectives, and to what extent can they be applied or adapted to the target context?	4.1
2: How suitable are ASAM-related standards—such as OpenXOntology, OpenODD, and OpenSCENARIO, which have been successfully applied in the automated driving domain—for modeling customer and user scenarios?	4.2
3: If ASAM-related standards prove to be suitable, how can a dedicated ontology-based, machine-readable model be constructed to formally represent customer and user scenarios, using the angle grinder as a case study?	4.4, 5.1
4: How can the proposed ontology-based, machine-readable model for customer and user scenarios be validated?	4.5

Table 26: Overview of research questions and the chapters where they are addressed

In the following, each research question is revisited and briefly answered

Research Question 1

The structured literature review in Section 4.1 revealed that while ontology-based scenario modeling has been applied across diverse domains (e.g., automated driving, semantic technologies, safety and protection, IoT), no existing method explicitly addressed customer and user perspectives in a product development context. Moreover, specific definitions of “customer scenarios” and “user scenarios” were largely absent in prior work. This confirmed a clear research gap.

Research Question 2

As pointed out in Section 5.2, the comparative analysis of ASAM standards showed differentiated applicability. OpenXOntology, with its layered structure of core and domain ontology, offers transferable principles for representing users, activities, devices, and environments, making it broadly suitable for adaptation. OpenODD provides a structured way to formalise environmental and contextual conditions and can be applied to user scenarios, but it lacks activity modeling and does not capture customer perspectives. By contrast, OpenSCENARIO remains tightly bound to dynamic traffic situations and is not transferable to non-driving domains.

Research Question 3

Within the framework of ASAM OpenXOntology, an initial ontology can be established by adapting the core ontology and extending the domain ontology (see Section 4.4). In the case of the angle grinder, this enrichment can be achieved through integration with methodologies such as CAMEOnto and through inductive insights derived from qualitative empirical scenario data.

Research Question 4

A validation approach was proposed in Section 4.5, inspired by Enhance methodology, based on a before-and-after experiment with hypotheses addressing coverage, detail, and connectivity of scenario descriptions. While the validation concept was clearly defined, its implementation was beyond the scope of this thesis. Therefore, validation remains a next step to be addressed in future research.

In summary, this thesis demonstrates both the feasibility and added value of ontology-based modeling for integrating customer and user perspectives. It provides a first structured, machine-readable scenario model for the angle grinder domain, while also identifying limitations and areas for refinement.

6.2 Outlook

While the proposed model provides a promising foundation, several avenues remain open for further research and development. This section distinguishes between short-term recommendations that build directly on the present work and broader future research directions.

6.2.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this thesis, several practical recommendations can be derived for advancing the developed ontology model:

- **Further Validation:** The ontology may be further validated by applying the approach described in Section 4.5 or by employing alternative evaluation methods. Such additional validation will help ensure its robustness and provide greater confidence in its applicability across different use cases.
- **Iterative Refinement of the Ontology:** Continuous refinement of the ontology is required to align it with evolving engineering practices and research findings. This entails modifying existing classes, enriching properties, and creating new instances derived from empirical studies and validation feedback. A structured refinement process would also ensure that the ontology remains flexible and adaptable to new requirements over time.
- **Continuous Improvement and Reuse Assessment:** The ontology should not only serve as a static knowledge structure but should also be used iteratively as a decision-support tool. By applying it repeatedly to real-world case studies, lessons learned from practice can be systematically captured, enabling the model to evolve into a repository of reusable knowledge. In particular, rule-based extensions (e.g., SWRL) may be expanded to semi-automatically evaluate scenarios, thereby generating improvement requirements and systematically assessing reuse potentials across multiple product generations.

6.2.2 Future Work

Beyond the immediate recommendations, several broader research directions open up promising opportunities for further development and impact:

- **Automation:** Manual ontology engineering is time-consuming and subject to inconsistencies. Future work should therefore focus on automation, for example by offering standardized Excel or CSV templates that can be imported into Protégé via the CSV plugin. Such workflows would enable semi-automatic creation and updating of ontology instances, reduce subjectivity, and ensure that the model remains consistent with evolving datasets.
- **Integration of Artificial Intelligence:** Advances in AI, in particular large language models such as ChatGPT, provide new opportunities for ontology engineering. AI could support the extraction of structured concepts from unstructured text, assist in refining

class hierarchies, and analyse or transform ontology output files. This integration would enhance both the efficiency and the intelligence of ontology maintenance, bringing the model closer to real-time applicability in engineering contexts.

- **Linking with Digital Engineering Tools:** To maximize practical utility, the ontology can also be integrated with existing digital engineering environments, such as CAD/PLM systems, digital twins, or simulation platforms. Such integration would enable automated scenario-driven evaluations, seamless data exchange, and advanced decision-support functionalities in early design phases.
- **Cross-domain Transfer and Scalability:** Finally, the dual-perspective methodology should be tested beyond the domain of power tools. Applying the approach to other product families and industrial sectors would allow a systematic evaluation of its scalability, adaptability, and generalisability. Such cross-domain studies would not only strengthen the validity of the model but also contribute to a broader understanding of ontology-based scenario modelling in circular product systems.

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Appendix

6.3 Template of Initial Workshop

User and customer scenarios Template

Challenges
My experience with and power tools so far...

Scenario Image

Szenario

<p>User/Customer </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Describe the user or customer who interacts with the angle grinder... ■ age ■ Experience ■ Position ■ ... 	<p>Angle Grinder </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Why I use an angle grinder... ■ Features ■ Usage hours ■ Polish ■ Cutting ■ ... 	<p>Workpiece </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ What I use the angle grinder for... ■ Material ■ Form ■ ...
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Environment

- The environment in which the angle grinder is used...
- Weather
- Temperature
- Construction site
- ...

Use-Case

- Use of the scenario: This is how I used the angle grinder to achieve my goal...

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an der Universität Karlsruhe (KIT)

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Figure 36: Workshop Template

6.4 Online sources reviewed for supplementary scenario data

Name	Description
<i>Angle Grinder Toolbox Talk</i>	Institutional safety bulletin detailing angle grinder hazard identification and safe operating practices.
<i>Angle Grinders – A Complete Buying Guide</i>	Comprehensive buyer’s guide covering grinder types, applications, safety features, and purchase considerations.
<i>Angle Grinder Buying Guide – For Cutting, Grinding, Polishing, Sanding</i>	Market-oriented guide outlining cutting, grinding, polishing, and sanding use-cases with tool recommendations.
<i>Angle Grinder Safety Guide</i>	Practitioner-focused overview of safety measures and PPE when using angle grinders in real-world scenarios.
<i>Arten von Winkelschleifern</i>	German-language content summarizing types of angle grinders, performance specs, and application domains.
<i>Winkelschleifer</i>	German blog providing contextual overview of grinder functions, user benefits, and potential hazards.
<i>Key Parts of an Angle Grinder</i>	Manufacturer blog explaining key components of angle grinders and their functional roles.

Table 27: Online sources reviewed for supplementary scenario data

6.5 Overview of main Ontology Properties

User scenario

Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ User [1]	Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ Location [1]
Location $\xrightarrow{\text{hasEnvironmentalCondition}}$ EnvironmentalCondition [1:n]	EnvironmentalCondition $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ environmentalConditionProperty [0:n]
User $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ userProperty [1:n]	User $\xrightarrow{\text{participantOf}}$ Activity [1:n]
Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasBeginning}}$ Event [0:1]	Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasEnding}}$ Event [0:1]
Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasTemporalPart}}$ Activity [0:n]	Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{involves}}$ Device [0:1]
Device $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ ToolComponent [0:n]	Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProcessingActivityObject}}$ Workpiece [0:1]
Workpiece $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ workPieceProperty [1:n]	

Table 28: Relations in the user scenario

Customer scenario

Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ Customer [1]	Scenario $\xrightarrow{\text{hasSocialEnvironmentCondition}}$ SocialEnvironmentCondition [1:n]
Customer $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ customerProperty [1:n]	Customer $\xrightarrow{\text{participantOf}}$ Activity [1:n]
Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasBeginning}}$ Event [0:1]	Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasEnding}}$ Event [0:1]
Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{occursAfter/Before}}$ Activity [0:n]	Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasTemporalPart}}$ Activity [0:n]
Activity $\xrightarrow{\text{hasActivityObject}}$ Device/physical&social Property [0:n]	Device $\xrightarrow{\text{hasComponent}}$ ToolComponent [0:n]
Device $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ physical&social Property [1:n]	SocialEnvironmentCondition $\xrightarrow{\text{hasProperty}}$ socialEnvironmentConditionProperty [0:n]

Table 29: Relations in the customer scenario ontology

6.6 Main classes of user and customer scenarios and mapping of HQDM core concepts

Domain Concept	Core Concept
Scenario	SystemState
User	WholeLifeSystemComponent
Location	WholeLifeSystemComponent
EnvironmentalCondition	PhysicalProperty
Activity	ActivityState
Workpiece	WholeLifeSystemComponent & WholeLifeOrdinaryPhysicalObject
Device	WholeLifeSystemComponent & WholeLifeOrdinaryPhysicalObject
ToolComponent	WholeLifeSystemComponent & WholeLifeOrdinaryPhysicalObject

Table 30: User cenario and mapping of HQDM core concepts

Domain Concept	Core Concept
Scenario	SystemState
Customer	WholeLifeSystemComponent
Activity	ActivityState
Device	WholeLifeSystemComponent & WholeLifeOrdinaryPhysicalObject
ToolComponent	WholeLifeSystemComponent & WholeLifeOrdinaryPhysicalObject
SocialEnvironmentCondition	SocialProperty

Table 31: Customer scenario and mapping of HQDM core concepts